

COMPARING SUSTAINABILITY COMPETENCES ACROSS SCHOOL CURRICULA IN EUROPE AND BEYOND

May 2025

Apoorwa Hooda and Orsolya Tuba
Glocal Minta Oy (Finn minta)

Inclusive Future: Fostering Inclusion through Sustainable Education (POL-EXP)

Acknowledgements

This Comparative Curricula Mapping Study was made possible through the collaborative efforts of the InclusiveFuture project partners, each contributing valuable insights and expertise. We express our sincere gratitude to the Center for Educational Integration of Children and Students from Ethnic Minorities (CEICSEM) and Law and Psychology (LP) in Bulgaria, Big Bang School (BBS) in Greece, Óbuda University (OE) and the Regional Centre for Information and Scientific Development (RCISD) in Hungary, Instituto Superior Técnico /Lisbon University Técnico Lisboa in Portugal, Focus Eco Center in Romania, Open Europe and Escola Pia de Catalunya (EPC) in Spain, and Konya Provincial National Education Directorate (Konya IL MEM) in Türkiye.

We also extend our heartfelt appreciation to the European Union for their generous funding, which has been instrumental in supporting this study and the broader goals of the InclusiveFuture project. Their commitment to fostering sustainable and inclusive education across Europe has provided the foundation for this important work.

Call: ERASMUS-EDU-2024-POL-EXP
Granting authority: European Education and Culture Executive Agency
Project number: 101195868
Project name: Inclusive Future: Fostering Inclusion through Sustainable Education
Project acronym: InclusiveFuture
Project website: <https://inclusive-future.eu/>

Table of Contents

Acknowledgements	1
Table of Contents	2
List of abbreviations	6
List of Tables and Figures	7
Glossary	8
Executive Summary	10
1. Introduction	13
1.1 About the Project	15
1.2 Purpose of the study	16
1.3 Study context	17
1.3.1 Participating countries and organizations	17
1.3.2 Underlying Sustainability Competence Framework	22
1.4 Research questions	24
1.5 Structure of the study report	24
2. Methodology	25
2.1 Individual Country Analysis	25
2.2 Comparative Analysis	26
3.3 Methodological Considerations	27
3. Country-wise analysis of National Core Curricula	28
3.1 Bulgaria	28
3.1.1 Overview of the Education System	28
3.1.2 Definitions	28
3.1.3 Four Dimensions of Sustainability	29
3.1.4 GreenComp Competence Areas in Bulgarian School Curricula	30
3.1.5 Teacher Education and Leadership Training	30
3.1.6 Assessment of Sustainability Competences	31
3.1.7 Identified Good Practices	31
3.1.8 Key Strengths and Gaps	31
3.2 Finland	32
3.2.1 Overview of the Education System	32
3.2.2 Definitions	33
3.2.3 Four Dimensions of Sustainability	33
3.2.4 GreenComp competence areas in Finnish School Curricula	34
3.2.5 Teacher Education and Leadership Training	35

3.2.6 Assessment of sustainability competences	35
3.2.7 Identified Good Practices	36
3.2.8 Key strengths and gaps	37
3.3 Greece	37
3.3.1 Overview of the Education System	37
3.3.2 Definitions	38
3.3.3 Four Dimensions of Sustainability	38
3.3.4 GreenComp Competence Areas in Greek School Curricula	39
3.3.5 Teacher Education and Leadership Training	40
3.3.6 Assessment of Sustainability Competences	41
3.3.7 Identified Good Practices	41
3.3.8 Key Strengths and Gaps	42
3.4 Hungary	43
3.4.1 Overview of the Education System	43
3.4.2 Definitions	43
3.4.3 Four Dimensions of Sustainability	43
3.4.4 GreenComp Competence Areas in Hungarian School Curricula	44
3.4.5 Teacher Education and Leadership Training	45
3.4.6 Identified Good Practices	46
3.4.7 Key Strengths and Gaps	47
3.4.8. The importance of climate change as a societal problem	47
3.5 Portugal	49
3.5.1 Overview of the Education System	49
3.5.2 Definitions	49
3.5.3 Four Dimensions of Sustainability	50
3.5.4 GreenComp Competence Areas in Portuguese School Curricula	51
3.5.5 Teacher Education and Leadership Training	51
3.5.6 Assessment of Sustainability Competences	52
3.5.7 Identified Good Practices	52
3.5.8 Key Strengths and Gaps	52
3.6 Romania	53
3.6.1 Overview of the Education System	53
3.6.2 Definitions	53
3.6.3 Four Dimensions of Sustainability	54
3.6.4 GreenComp Competence Areas in Romanian School Curricula	54
3.6.5 Teacher Education and Leadership Training	56
3.6.6 Identified Good Practices	57
3.6.7 Assessment of Sustainability Competences	58

3.6.8 Key Strengths and Gaps	58
3.7 Spain	59
3.7.1 Overview of the Education System	59
3.7.2 Definitions	59
3.7.4 GreenComp Competence Areas in Spanish School Curricula	60
3.7.5 Teacher Education and Leadership Training	62
3.7.6 Identified Good Practices	63
3.7.7 Assessment of Sustainability Competences	63
3.7.8 Key Strengths and Gaps	63
3.8 Türkiye	64
3.8.1 Overview of the Education System	64
3.8.2 Definitions	64
3.8.3 Four Dimensions of Sustainability	64
3.8.4 GreenComp Competence Areas	65
3.8.5 Teacher Education and Leadership Training	66
3.8.6 Good Practices	67
3.8.7 Assessment of Sustainability Competences	67
3.8.8 Key Strengths and Gaps	67
4. Cross-Country comparative analysis/synthesis	69
4.1 Commonalities across countries	69
4.2 Differences and country-specific challenges	70
Bulgaria	70
Finland	70
Greece	70
Hungary	70
Portugal	71
Romania	71
Spain	71
Türkiye	71
Comparative Analysis and Overarching Challenges	72
4.3 Overall alignment with GreenComp	72
4.3.1 General Trends	72
4.3.2 Definitions of sustainability and related terms	74
4.3.3 Alignment with GreenComp Competence Areas	77
4.3.3 Country-wise mapping of GreenComp competence Areas	78
4.4 Areas of improvement	80

5. Readiness Assessment	82
5.1 Inclusion Readiness	85
5.2 Comparative Analysis of Inclusion	86
Bulgaria	86
Finland	87
Greece	88
Hungary	89
Portugal	90
Romania	90
Spain	91
Türkiye	91
6. Recommendations and Next Steps	95
6.1 General Recommendations for Policy Makers (EU or Global)	95
6.2 Country-Specific Recommendations and Reflections	95
6.3 Teacher Education Programs (For Pre-Service Teachers)	98
6.4 Teacher Professional Development Programs (For In-Service Teachers)	99
6.5 Support for School Leaders	100
6.6 Next Steps for the Project	100
6.7 Risk Factors and Mitigation Suggestions	101
7. Conclusion	103
8. Bibliography	104

Tables and Figures

Figure 1: Participating countries and number of partner organizations (*associated partners) represented on a map.

Figure 2. Transversal competences in basic education in Finland (Halinen, 2018)

Figure 3: Adaptation - Public Climate Change Attitudes Index, source: NATÉR (dark orange: Attitude much more favourable than the national average. light yellow: Attitude less favourable than the national average)

Figure 4: Adaptation - The importance of climate change as a societal issue, source: NATÉR (dark yellow: climate change prioritised above the national average Light yellow: Climate change ranked lower than the national average)

Figure 5: 8th grade students' sustainability values and action competence for sustainability (Source: European Commission Joint Research Centre, calculations based on IEA ICCS 2022)

Table 1: Mapping of key sustainability related definitions across countries' curricula with GreenComp definitions

Table 2: Mapping the four competence areas of the GreenComp framework with countries' curricula

Table 3. Comparative Assessment of Sustainability Competence Readiness

Table 4: Comparative Assessment of Inclusion Readiness across countries

List of abbreviations

Abbreviation	Term
CPD	Continuing Professional Development
EASNIE	European Agency for Special Needs and Inclusive Education
ESD	Education for Sustainable Development
EU	European Union
GCI	GreenComp Curriculum Integration
GreenComp	European Sustainability Competence Framework
IE	Inclusive Education
K–12	Kindergarten to Grade 12
OECD	Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development
SD	Sustainable Development
SDG	Sustainable Development Goals
SDG 4	Sustainable Development Goal 4
SIIE	Sustainable Intercultural and Inclusive Education
TT	Teacher Training
UN	United Nations
UNESCO	United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization
VET	Vocational Education and Training

Glossary

Term	Definition
Action Competence	The ability to act intentionally and effectively in sustainability-related issues with confidence and responsibility (Mogensen & Schnack, 2010).
Collective Action	Collaborative efforts by groups to address shared sustainability issues or achieve common goals (UNESCO, 2020).
Critical Emotional Awareness	Understanding and managing emotions in relation to sustainability challenges, enabling empathy, resilience, and social responsibility (UNESCO, 2020).
Critical Thinking	The ability to question norms, evaluate evidence, and reflect on assumptions to support informed decision-making in sustainability contexts (UNESCO, 2017).
Eco-Social Education	An educational approach that integrates ecological and social dimensions, emphasizing the interconnectedness of environmental, social, and economic systems and promoting values of sustainability and social justice.
Four Dimensions of Sustainability	The environmental, social, economic, and cultural dimensions that underpin comprehensive approaches to sustainability (UNESCO, 2017).
Futures Thinking / Futures Literacy	The capacity to imagine and evaluate possible future scenarios and make informed choices to shape sustainable futures (Miller, 2015).
Global Citizenship Education	Education that aims to equip learners with the knowledge, skills, values, and attitudes they need to contribute to a more just, peaceful, tolerant, inclusive, secure, and sustainable world.
Holistic Education	An approach to education that integrates intellectual, emotional, social, physical, artistic, creative, and spiritual potentials of learners (UNESCO, 2020).
Individual Initiative	Personal motivation and proactivity in engaging with sustainability challenges and solutions (Bianchi, Pisiotis, & Cabrera Giraldez, 2022).
Planetary Well-being	A concept that frames human well-being within the ecological limits of Earth's systems, linking health, sustainability, and equity (Kortetmäki et al., 2021).

Political Agency	The capacity of individuals or groups to influence decision-making and advocate for sustainability policies and practices (UNESCO, 2020).
Systems Thinking	Understanding the interconnections and interdependencies within ecological, social, and economic systems (Bianchi et al., 2022).
Valuing Sustainability	Recognising the importance of sustainability for present and future generations, and integrating these values into personal and collective actions (Bianchi et al., 2022).
Transversal Competences	Knowledge, skills, values, attitudes, and will applicable across various subjects and contexts.
Ecosocial Knowledge and Ability	Understanding and ability to act in ways that consider both ecological and social dimensions, emphasizing climate change awareness and responsible lifestyles.
Action-oriented competencies	Skills and abilities focused on taking practical action and initiative in sustainability-related contexts.

Executive Summary

Comparing Sustainability Competences Across School Curricula in Europe and Beyond

InclusiveFuture: Fostering Inclusion through Sustainable Education

This document presents a comprehensive comparative analysis of how sustainability competences are integrated into the primary and secondary education curricula of eight partner countries: Bulgaria, Finland, Greece, Hungary, Portugal, Romania, Spain, and Türkiye. Undertaken as part of the InclusiveFuture project, funded by the European Union, the study aims to evaluate the readiness and relevance of national core curricula regarding sustainability competence development and assessment based on the GreenComp Framework (2022) of the European Union. The project's mission is to embed sustainability competences into school curricula, fostering environmentally conscious individuals prepared to contribute positively to the planet's future.

Sustainability and sustainable development are globally recognized as vital for enhancing quality of life, intergenerational equity, and environmental conservation. The InclusiveFuture project addresses the urgent planetary need, as outlined in the GreenComp framework, to integrate sustainability competences into life-long learning, developing learners with the knowledge, skills, and attitudes to think, plan, and act responsibly for the planet. The project aims to support the integration of sustainability competences into the schooling and educational process, creating a more inclusive environment and empowering primary and secondary schools towards sustainable practices. Aligned with the European Education Area's priorities, the project facilitates inclusive education, advocates for education for sustainable development (ESD), and contributes to the European Skills Agenda. The purpose of this study is to evaluate the state of ESD in partner countries' national core curricula and selected practices and mapping the findings with the GreenComp Framework.

The study employs a qualitative content analysis approach, examining key policy and curricular documents from each country. These documents include national core curricula, educational laws, strategic frameworks, supporting guidelines, and possible research papers on Education for Sustainable Development. The analysis identifies how sustainability-related concepts, skills, and values are addressed, focusing on environmental, social, cultural, and economic dimensions of sustainability. The GreenComp framework served as the central reference, and findings from each country were synthesized into structured reports. A cross-country comparative analysis identifies similarities, differences, and broader trends

across participating nations, highlighting best practices and recommendations for strengthening sustainability education.

Country-wise Analysis Highlights

- Bulgaria: Prioritizes human rights and inclusivity, integrating sustainability themes across subjects. Initiatives like the Eco-schools program and national conferences support teacher training, but consistent support and assessment methods are needed.
- Finland: Strong emphasis on student well-being and equity, with a well-defined concept of ecosocial knowledge and ability. Integrates GreenComp competences effectively through multidisciplinary learning and student-led initiatives, though a national tool for explicitly assessing sustainability competences is lacking.
- Greece: Focuses on interdisciplinary, inclusive, and human-centered education with a growing integration of sustainability themes. Needs more structured implementation and teacher training.
- Hungary: Believes in balanced progress across social, economic, and environmental pillars. Faces challenges in updating curriculum and providing adequate teacher training for sustainability education.
- Portugal: Committed to sustainable development through various national strategies. Encourages environmental education and global citizenship but needs to increase teacher preparedness.
- Romania: Shows increasing commitment through national strategies for sustainable development. Prioritizes environmental protection and social inclusion but requires significant reforms and teacher preparation.
- Spain: Implements the 2030 Agenda through policies promoting green transition and social equity. Integrating sustainability at all levels of education remains difficult.
- Türkiye: Demonstrates a strong commitment by integrating SDGs into national education strategies. Promotes sustainability through curriculum integration and teacher training, but needs further support for educators.

Countries share a commitment to bringing sustainability mindsets and practices into education, recognizing the need for long-term change in mindsets. However, implementation varies due to geographical, social, and economic challenges. Commonalities include integrating sustainability across subjects and acknowledging the importance of teacher training. Differences arise in the depth and scope of sustainability integration, the clarity of definitions, and the support provided for assessment. All countries generally align

with GreenComp, but the degree of integration varies. Common areas for improvement include consistent teacher training, systematic assessment of sustainability competences, and more practical, hands-on learning experiences for both learners and educators, including pupils, teachers and school principals.

Readiness Assessment

Readiness levels for including GreenComp sustainability competence areas differ. Finland shows high readiness due to its well-defined concept of ecosocial knowledge and comprehensive curriculum integration. Bulgaria, Spain, and Türkiye are making significant strides but need further implementation and teacher training. Greece, Hungary, Portugal, and Romania have shown increasing commitment but require more substantial reforms. Inclusion readiness varies, with countries recognizing the importance of addressing vulnerable groups. General observations from focus groups indicate a need for more resources, support, and practical tools for teachers to implement sustainability education effectively.

Recommendations and Next Steps

General recommendations for policymakers include providing more resources and support for schools, developing national assessment tools, and ensuring consistent and relevant teacher training focused on sustainability issues in education. Country-specific recommendations address individual challenges and needs. For teacher education programs, it is recommended to integrate sustainability into both pre-service and in-service training, and for school leaders, it is recommended to support whole-school approaches, teacher collaboration within the school, as well as inter-school collaborations. Next steps for the project involve strengthening the findings through empirical data, and eventual development of an inclusive pedagogical model for teaching, learning, and assessing sustainability competences, providing guidance to teachers and educators.

Conclusion

This study highlights the progress and challenges in integrating sustainability competences into school curricula across eight partner countries. While all countries show commitment, variations in implementation and readiness indicate a need for continued support and development. The InclusiveFuture project plays a vital role in facilitating this integration, contributing to a more sustainable and inclusive future.

1. Introduction

One of the most pressing duties of humanities in this age, as outlined in the GreenComp Framework (Bianchi et al., 2022) is to ensure a fair and decent livelihood for all people, regenerate nature and enable biodiversity to thrive. As a means of fostering positive transformation, the concept of sustainable development and sustainability have garnered worldwide acknowledgment with a focus on enhancing quality of life, intergenerational equity, and environmental conservation (UNESCO, 2009; Lozano, 2011; Lambrechts, Van Liedekerke, & Van Petegem, 2018). Countries in Europe and beyond, including the 8 countries participating in the InclusiveFuture project, have committed to the sustainable development goals (SDGs), 2030.

Bulgaria's policies prioritize human rights, gender equality, and inclusivity, ensuring no one is left behind. This principle is central to key Bulgaria's strategic documents focused on including persons with disabilities, vulnerable groups, Roma, youth, the elderly, and disadvantaged children. It is also committed to actively involving all sectors of the society in the achievement of the SDGs as the achievement of the 2030 agenda cannot be achieved by the governments alone (United Nations Department of Economic and Social Affairs [UN DESA], 2022). Hence, sustainable development, including all three dimensions of it, is an important priority for the government of Bulgaria.

Finland is at the forefront of many international sustainability comparisons and studies and is close to reaching many of the SDGs related to social and economic sustainability (UN DESA, 2022). Finland's [development policy priorities](#) promote the achievement of the SDGs. Finland promotes sustainable development especially in its areas of expertise, which include education and enhancing the position and rights of girls and women. In Finland's view, the promotion of equality, inclusive education, technology, digitalisation and innovation plays an important role in the delivery of the SDG (Ministry for Foreign Affairs of Finland, 2025).

Greece has promptly integrated the goals and principles of Sustainable Development, as defined by the United Nations, shaping its economic, educational, social, and cultural policies accordingly. In the field of education, it has already incorporated principles such as democracy, citizenship, and active civic engagement by organizing Skills Workshops, introducing relevant thematic areas, and empowering educators through appropriate training, guidelines, and holistic, interdisciplinary methodologies. This includes the promotion of critical thinking, open dialogue, digital literacy, and STEAM workshops, among others.

Hungary believes that sustainable development requires balanced progress across its three pillars. The social pillar is supported by a holistic family policy aimed at empowering families and addressing demographic challenges. The economic pillar is strengthened through

initiatives to boost productivity, expand employment, and promote a knowledge- and innovation-based economy. Environmental sustainability remains central, with clean water and sanitation seen as critical for development and peace. In 2017, Hungary established a multi-stakeholder platform to support the 2030 Agenda, involving the Hungarian Central Statistical Office (HCSO), CSOs, academia, and business. The HCSO reports that 75% of global SDG indicators are available in Hungary.

Portugal has progressively reinforced its commitment to sustainable development in various national strategies and policy instruments in line with the [2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development](#). It believes that it's time for education to have its fair share in the promotion of sustainable thinking in Portuguese society. The Ministry of Education encourages environmental education and global citizenship by identifying competencies in the Perfil dos Alunos à Saída da Escolaridade Obrigatória (Profile of Students at the end of the Compulsory Education), which include responsibility, criticality and ecological consciousness.

Romania has shown increasing commitment to sustainable development through the adoption of national strategies aligned with the 2030 Agenda, including the National Strategy for Sustainable Development (2022–2030) and the National Strategy for Environmental and Climate Education. These actions prioritize environmental protection, social inclusion, and equitable access to education, with a focus on engaging youth and vulnerable groups. Romania promotes sustainability through intersectoral collaboration and by integrating key SDG principles into education, public policy, and community development initiatives.

In **Spain**, the 2030 Agenda is implemented through policies that promote the green transition with renewable energy and climate action, as well as measures to reduce inequalities and advance gender equality. It also supports sustainable economic growth based on innovation, decent work, and digital transformation.

Türkiye demonstrates a strong commitment to the 2030 Agenda by integrating the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) into national education, environment, and social inclusion strategies. The country's "11th Development Plan" and "National Voluntary Reviews" emphasize inclusive growth, environmental protection, and quality education as key priorities. In line with the GreenComp Framework, Türkiye promotes sustainability in education through curriculum integration, teacher training, and digital transformation. Initiatives such as the "Green School Programme" and the inclusion of environmental awareness in the updated national curriculum reflect a growing focus on ecological literacy and student agency. Türkiye also prioritizes the inclusion of disadvantaged groups—such as persons with disabilities, migrants, and economically vulnerable populations—ensuring that no one is left behind. The Ministry of National Education of Türkiye supports sustainability through strategic action plans and partnerships with civil society, aiming to empower both educators and learners to become active agents of change.

What is common across the countries' commitment to the SDGs is to bring sustainability mindsets and practices into education, as the policy agreements, financial incentives and technological innovations are not enough if a long term change in mindsets has to be achieved. In order for the changes to be long lasting and for the planet to be livable for future generations, a commitment to integrating sustainability issues and practices into life-long learning is needed (Bianchi et al., 2022).

The InclusiveFuture project's mission to embed sustainability competencies into school curricula and to cultivate a generation of environmentally conscious individuals who are prepared to contribute positively to the planet's future is built on this larger global need to integrate sustainability in life-long learning through development of sustainability competences, i.e., the knowledge, skills and attitudes required for learners to think, plan and act with empathy, responsibility and care for our planet (Bianchi et al., 2022).

1.1 About the Project

The InclusiveFuture project, funded by the European Union, aims to support the integration of sustainability competences into the educational process which will lead to a more inclusive environment for teachers and learners and will empower the transition of schools towards sustainable and inclusive practices.

Recognizing the imperative for nurturing sustainability competences from a young age, this project concentrates on Topic 4: School education, with a focus on Priority 9: Building sustainability competences. Aligned with this priority, the project's objectives are intricately connected to the priorities of the European Education Area (EEA):

1. Facilitating Inclusive education: The project endeavours to offer avenues for the development of sustainability competences among primary and secondary school students, including those from vulnerable groups and rural areas such as migrants, refugees, and ethnic minorities. It aims to establish frameworks for nurturing such competences among these groups.

2. Advocating education for sustainable development (ESD): Inspired by the Council Recommendation on Learning for the Green Transition and Sustainable Development and the European Sustainability Competence Framework, the project aims to develop comprehensive educational curricula tailored to various age groups and educational levels. These curricula will integrate concepts of sustainability, environmental conservation, and green technologies, aligning with the European Sustainability Competence Framework. Additionally, the project will provide training programs for educators to enhance their capacity in delivering ESD effectively.

The transnational cooperation facilitated by this project will contribute to the European Skills Agenda by fostering innovative policy approaches that have the potential to enhance education and training systems across Europe. The overarching objective of the project is to

influence policy in school education by developing innovative approaches to integrating sustainable competences in schools across Europe. The project aims to integrate sustainability competences into school curricula, directly addressing the Erasmus+ priority of promoting education for sustainable development. By developing comprehensive curriculum models and providing professional development for teachers, the project ensures that students acquire critical sustainability competences. This is in line with the objectives of the GreenComp, which emphasizes the importance of equipping learners with the skills needed to address environmental challenges and promote sustainable lifestyles.

1.2 Purpose of the study

The need to integrate sustainability competences across primary and secondary education systems arises from several overarching challenges, including climate change, environmental degradation, social inequalities and the need for a transition to a greener, more inclusive economy. Although the importance of sustainability education is internationally recognised, there is still a significant gap in the practical implementation and assessment of sustainability competences within school curricula of countries in Europe and beyond (Wiek, Withycombe, & Redman, 2011; UNESCO, 2020). There is a need to strengthen the implementation of GreenComp competence development framework (Bianchi, 2022) across European schools by providing teachers with pedagogy, tools and resources. Providing support in evaluating and assessing the development of sustainability competences is imperative, as the GreenComp and other frameworks are not easy to implement due to their policy nature. Adapting these essential policy and guiding documents to teachers and learners are crucial to support inclusion and sustainability. This is supported by conclusions of the recent Eurydice report on Learning for sustainability.

As a first step towards providing support to schools across partner countries in integrating and assessing the development of sustainability competences, it is crucial to understand the countries' latest progress and existing needs with respect to Education for Sustainable Development (ESD) so far. Hence in the first phase of the project,

As a part of the above mentioned endeavour, this comparative study **aims to evaluate the state of art concerning education for sustainable development (ESD) in the national core curricula and selected practices of 8 partner countries** through analysis of each country's primary and secondary school curricula as well as supporting documents. The main focus throughout the study is on **evaluating the readiness and relevance of national core curricula of partner countries regarding sustainability competence development and assessment based on the GreenComp Framework (2022)**. The curricular analysis is supported by provision of evidence on teacher training and assessment practices regarding development of sustainability competences provided by partner countries.

In a follow-up report published separately, the consortium collects empirical data in the form of focus group discussions, on the best practices, needs, challenges and barriers of

schools to integrate and assess sustainability competences into their education in partner countries. The findings from this study as well as the focus group report will be used later to develop an inclusive pedagogical model for teaching, learning and assessment of sustainability competences in schools, which will provide guidance to teachers and educators working with development of sustainable competences at the school level.

1.3 Study context

1.3.1 Participating countries and organizations

Data was collected from the eight listed countries through the following partner organizations of the InclusiveFuture project (see fig.1):

1. Bulgaria

- a. The Center for Educational Integration of Children and Students from Ethnic Minorities (CEICSEM) in Bulgaria is a government-supported institution focused on promoting equal educational opportunities for children from ethnic minority backgrounds. It works to integrate students into the education system, support bilingual education, and foster intercultural dialogue. The centre develops policies, funds projects, and collaborates with NGOs and schools to reduce educational disparities.
- b. Law and Psychology (LP), a non-profit organisation based in Bulgaria. The main activities of the organization are focused on enhancing the development of skills and competences of youth and vulnerable groups; organizing training, conferences and seminars; supporting Law and Psychology students during their internship, as well as conducting research in the field of Bulgarian, European and international legislation.

2. Finland

- a. Glocal Minta OY (GM), is a globally connected SME located in Jyväskylä, Finland, at the heart of education development, with its focus on sustainability and global citizenship education (www.finnminta.com/en). GM fosters dialogue and development both in Finland and globally. It specializes in education for sustainable development, planetary well-being education, action competence for well-being, phenomenon-based and interdisciplinary learning. Its expertise extends to educational research and innovation, framework development, and collaborative, comparative research processes, driving meaningful advancements in education worldwide. Its initiatives, such as sustainability theme weeks and Finn Minta Forum teacher training events, provide practical and experiential learning and dissemination opportunities.

3. Greece

- a. Big Bang School (BBS), an innovative primary school established in 2019 on the border of Thessaloniki and Halkidiki, was founded by visionary educators to provide a holistic learning experience for students from across Greece on three core principles: improvement of consciousness, development of life skills, and teaching through differentiated learning. In an environment that nurtures curiosity, personal growth, and a deep appreciation for knowledge and nature, the students at BBS are empowered to shape the future. Through educational field trips, interactive workshops, artistic activities, and collaborative projects, students cultivate their talents, develop critical thinking skills, and enhance their social engagement. BBS fosters a strong connection with nature, creating a dynamic learning environment that encourages collaboration, discovery, and personal development—shaping responsible, innovative, and creative individuals. Embracing the principles of multilingualism from an early age, we explore the interaction of languages and cultures in the human brain, equipping students with valuable linguistic and intercultural skills. The school's vision is to create a transformative learning environment for every student, preparing them for the future and helping them become the best versions of themselves.

4. Hungary

- a. [Regional Centre for Information and Scientific Development \(RCISD\)](#), an innovative, women-lead SME, holds extensive experience in fostering inclusive educational practices and combating inequalities through international cooperation. RCISD excels in projects like the Hungarian Researchers' Night and Inclusion4Schools, promoting interdisciplinary collaboration and inclusivity in education. Through initiatives like STEAMCRAFT, they engage students in experiential learning, while projects like BIOLOC and CELEBio highlight sustainable development. Integrating RCISD's expertise into sustainability education ensures inclusivity and innovative learning.
- b. Obuda University (OE) is a key player in Hungarian higher education and a leading practice-oriented institution, where 11,000 students pursue their studies. According to the latest, 2024 Times Higher Education report, OU is the highest ranked technical university in Hungary. It offers competitive knowledge in the fields of mechanical engineering, mechatronic engineering, computer science, applied mathematics, economics, geoinformatics, architecture, marketing and teacher training in 7 faculties, 2 education centres, 16 BA/BSc (8 in English), and 14 MA/MSc (7 in English) programs. OU runs 3 doctoral schools. OU is an actor in multiple international organisations

and bilateral and international programmes (currently over 20 EU financed scientific projects).

5. Portugal

- a. Instituto Superior Técnico /Lisbon University Técnico Lisboa is Portugal's leading school of Engineering, Science, Technology, and Architecture, recognized for academic excellence, research impact, and strong international partnerships. With over 11,000 students from 60+ nationalities, Técnico fosters innovation, entrepreneurship, and cutting-edge research to address global challenges. The school actively participates in international academic networks (CLUSTER, TIME, CESAER) and collaborates with top universities such as MIT, CMU, UT-Austin, and EPFL through double degree and joint PhD programs. Técnico is committed to expanding its global presence through strategic partnerships, interdisciplinary research, and knowledge transfer, making it a key player in international projects.

6. Romania

- a. Focus Eco Center is a non-profit organization based in Tg. Mures, Romania, and is mainly active in the Central Transylvania region. The main goal of the organization is to collect and distribute quality information on key environmental issues, such as climate change or biodiversity loss, and to promote valuable, scientifically proven information on solutions. Focus believes that school teachers and educators are the right people who can influence the future of generations to come, so our main target groups are schools, but also works with other groups such as policy makers. It develops pilot projects especially in the field of water management and offers its experiences for implementation by larger systems.

7. Spain

- a. Open Europe is a non-profit organization based in Reus, Spain, dedicated to promoting European mobility, lifelong learning, and educational innovation. It provides training, career guidance, and access to European programs for students and educators. Open Europe specializes in fostering inclusion, sustainability, and digital skills, creating educational platforms and innovative learning resources to support professional development and social integration.
- b. Escola Pia de Catalunya (EPC) is an institution with a network of 23 schools. The studies go from kindergarten to higher education. We have VET studies in 13 of the 22 schools, in different fields: Administration, IT, Sport, Health care, Childhood, Marketing, forestry, hospitality etc. EPC has 20.000 students, 2.900 teachers, and one foundation (Camins). EPC has more than 400 years of experience in education in Catalunya. Since then, and up until today, the

Escola Pia de Catalunya has continued to evolve, adapting to new times without ever losing the purpose of promoting education as a driving force for social transformation.

8. Türkiye

- a. Konya Provincial National Education Directorate (Konya IL MEM) is a state institution responsible for the planning and coordination of educational and training activities in preschool, primary, secondary, and adult education throughout Konya. The province encompasses 31 districts, hosting a total of 2,913 schools, 36,439 teachers, and 543,379 students. Konya IL MEM acts as an umbrella organization, uniting this extensive educational network.

Figure 1: Participating countries and number of partner organizations (*associated partners) represented on a map.

The listed countries, despite their individual governments' strong commitment to the SDG4 goals, to a varied extent, continue to face multiple geographical, social and economic challenges, i.e., problems that can be categorized as sustainability issues, catering to the different dimensions of sustainability. Country-specific contexts with respect to education for sustainable development are explained below:

In **Bulgaria**, education for environmental sustainability is gaining interest, but its integration into the curriculum remains a challenge. Although environmental issues are covered in several subjects, there are still inconsistencies in the implementation and depth of

coverage. Teachers often lack adequate training and resources to teach these topics effectively. Only 15% of teachers report having received training in environmental education (Ministry of Education and Science, 2020).

Spain is highly vulnerable to climate change, especially in the Mediterranean region, a recognised climate change "hotspot". Rising temperatures and extreme weather events such as droughts and unpredictable rainfall patterns threaten key resources such as water and soil, which are crucial for agriculture, livestock, forestry and tourism (IPCC, 2021). The Spanish education system reflects these national priorities, with sustainability topics increasingly being integrated into the curriculum. However, it remains difficult to integrate these topics at all levels of education and in all regions. The Spanish Circular Economy Strategy (EEEC) aims to move from a linear to a circular economy and promote the reuse, recycling and repair of products by 2030 (Ministry of Ecological Transition, 2020).

Hungary is facing major environmental challenges, particularly in relation to water management and pollution. Despite efforts to address these issues, Hungary ranks 23rd out of 27 EU countries in the 2021 Environmental Performance Index (EPI, 2021). The current curriculum needs to be updated to enable comprehensive sustainability education. Teacher training programmes that focus on sustainability are crucial, as only 20% of Hungarian teachers say they are confident in teaching environmental topics (OECD, 2020).

Romania, rich in biodiversity, faces environmental threats from industrial activities. In the Environmental Performance Index 2021 (EPI, 2021), the country ranks 26th out of 27 EU countries. Despite some progress, significant reforms are needed to integrate sustainability into the education system. Only 10% of teachers feel adequately prepared to teach environmental sustainability (Ministry of Education, 2020).

Finland is a global leader in education, ranking 3rd in the Environmental Performance Index 2021 (EPI, 2021). The country has a robust foundation in environmental education, with 95% of schools incorporating sustainability into their curricula (Finnish National Agency for Education, 2020). Teacher training programs and professional development opportunities focusing on sustainability are essential for maintaining and enhancing this leadership position. By promoting interactive and learner-centred teaching methods, Finland continues to set a benchmark for integrating sustainability competencies across all levels of education and subjects, fostering a deep understanding of environmental issues among students. However, increasing migration and diversity in Finnish schools have brought about rising inequalities, both in general and specifically in education. As the student population becomes more diverse, disparities in educational outcomes and access to resources have emerged. Addressing these inequalities is crucial for ensuring that all students, regardless of their background, benefit equally from Finland's educational advancements and sustainability initiatives.

Greece faces severe environmental challenges due to climate change, with a projected 30% decrease in water availability by 2050 (European Environment Agency, 2021). The integration of comprehensive sustainability education into the curriculum is essential to meet these challenges. Education and training programmes for teachers that focus on sustainability are crucial. Only 25% of Greek teachers feel prepared to teach these topics (Ministry of Education and Religious Affairs, 2020).

Portugal has made significant progress in the field of education, but faces the challenge of integrating sustainability into the education system. Although Portugal scores well on various sustainability metrics, only 15% of teachers feel adequately prepared to teach environmental sustainability (Ministry of Education, 2020). The country ranks 17th out of 27 EU countries in the 2021 Environmental Performance Index (EPI, 2021), indicating room for improvement.

Türkiye faces significant environmental degradation and urbanisation issues, ranking 56th out of 180 countries in the 2021 Environmental Performance Index (EPI, 2021). Environmental challenges such as deforestation, water pollution, and waste management are compounded by rapid urbanisation. Integrating environmental sustainability into the curriculum is essential to address these challenges effectively. However, only 30% of Turkish teachers report feeling confident in teaching environmental topics (OECD, 2020).

1.3.2 Underlying Sustainability Competence Framework

The **GreenComp framework** (Bianchi, 2022), used as a reference framework in this study, is the European Union's official framework for developing sustainability competencies across all areas of education and training. Developed by the Joint Research Centre (JRC) as part of the European Green Deal, GreenComp aims to empower individuals of all ages to live, learn, and work in ways that support ecological, social, and economic sustainability. It provides a shared foundation for promoting a sustainability mindset across formal, non-formal, and informal learning environments.

At the heart of GreenComp is the belief that meaningful action for sustainability requires more than just knowledge—it requires the ability to think systemically, envision change, and act ethically. To this end, the framework organizes 12 key competences into four interconnected areas:

- 1. Embodying Sustainability Values** – This area focuses on internalizing values that support sustainability. It includes:
 - Valuing Sustainability: Reflecting on personal and societal values in relation to sustainable living.
 - Supporting Fairness: Promoting social and intergenerational equity.

- Promoting Nature: Recognizing human-nature interdependence and fostering care for ecosystems.

2. Embracing Complexity in Sustainability – This area cultivates the skills needed to understand and address complex, interconnected sustainability challenges. It includes:

- Systems Thinking: Seeing the bigger picture and interrelations across systems.
- Critical Thinking: Evaluating information, questioning assumptions, and resisting greenwashing.
- Problem Framing: Understanding sustainability issues from multiple perspectives and defining them appropriately.

3. Envisioning Sustainable Futures – Learners are encouraged to imagine and shape possible futures. This area includes:

- Futures Literacy: Anticipating and planning for alternative futures.
- Adaptability: Navigating change and making informed decisions under uncertainty.
- Exploratory Thinking: Using creativity and interdisciplinary approaches to generate new solutions.

4. Acting for Sustainability – This area emphasizes taking initiative and influencing change. It includes:

- Political Agency: Understanding governance systems and advocating for policy change.
- Collective Action: Collaborating with others for sustainable outcomes.
- Individual Initiative: Identifying and exercising one's own capacity to contribute meaningfully.

GreenComp is not a prescriptive curriculum but a reference model. It is designed to inform curriculum development, teacher education, policy design, and assessment strategies. The competences are non-hierarchical and interrelated, meant to be adapted to different learning levels and contexts.

The development of the framework was guided by a participatory methodology, drawing insights from educators, researchers, policymakers, and youth organizations across Europe. While it is broad in scope and not yet tested across all contexts, GreenComp is intended as a living document—flexible, evolving, and adaptable to new sustainability challenges.

Beyond its comprehensiveness and European relevance, GreenComp's flexibility is a significant advantage for this curricular mapping study. Its competence-based structure

allows for the identification of diverse approaches to integrating sustainability across various subjects and educational levels, rather than being tied to specific content. Furthermore, the framework's development through a participatory methodology, involving experts and stakeholders from various backgrounds, ensures that it represents a wide range of perspectives on sustainability education, making it a robust and widely accepted reference point for comparison across different national contexts. This inclusive development process enhances its legitimacy and applicability for analyzing diverse curricula.

1.4 Research questions

The following research questions are attempted to be answered in this study:

1. How do InclusiveFuture partner countries' national curricula address sustainability competence development and assessment as outlined in the GreenComp framework?
2. What are the key similarities and differences in how sustainability issues are incorporated into the curricula of partner countries?
3. How do countries compare in terms of readiness levels in including GreenComp sustainability competence areas in their curricula?

1.5 Structure of the study report

This report provides a comprehensive analysis of sustainability competence development within national core curricula across eight partner countries. It begins with an introduction to the InclusiveFuture project, outlining its goals and alignment with European educational priorities, and defines the purpose and scope of the study including the research questions. The methodology section details the research design, document analysis approach, and any tools or technologies used in the process, followed by a thorough country-wise analysis of national core curricula, focusing on Bulgaria, Finland, Greece, Hungary, Portugal, Romania, Spain, and Türkiye. The cross-country comparative analysis synthesizes findings, highlighting commonalities, differences, country-specific challenges, and overall alignment with the GreenComp framework. It also assesses each country's readiness in including GreenComp sustainability competence areas and identifies examples of good practices and common areas for improvement. The readiness assessment delves deeper into the specific preparedness of each country to implement sustainability competences and inclusion readiness. Finally, the report concludes with recommendations and next steps, followed by references and optional annexes, providing a holistic view of the current state and future directions for integrating sustainability competences into education.

2. Methodology

This compiled curricular mapping study presents a comparative analysis of how sustainability is integrated into the primary and secondary education curricula of several European countries. The study involved a systematic mapping of the countries' curricular documents against the European Competence Framework for Sustainability (GreenComp) to identify common trends, unique approaches, strengths, and gaps in sustainability education across the participating nations.

2.1 Individual Country Analysis

Each country's analysis followed a broadly consistent methodological framework, allowing for cross-national comparison. The core steps in this process were:

- Document Selection:
 - Each country's project partner/s' team began by identifying the key policy and curricular documents that define primary and secondary education. This typically included the national core curriculum, educational laws, strategic frameworks, and relevant ordinances or guidelines.
 - The selection criteria emphasized official documents that outline mandatory educational content and learning objectives for all primary and secondary schools (ISCED 1-3 according to [ISCED classification 2011](#)) within the country, with the exception of Romania which included documents for primary and lower secondary education (ISCED 1-2).
 - Additional supportive documents, such as teacher education and training guidelines or latest research studies on the current status of education for sustainable development in primary and secondary schools were also included to provide a more comprehensive view of sustainability education.
- Curriculum Analysis:
 - The core of the methodology involved a detailed analysis of the selected documents to identify how sustainability-related concepts, skills, and values are addressed through a **qualitative content analysis** approach.
 - This analysis focused on:
 - How "sustainability," "sustainable development," and "sustainability competence" are defined (or implied) within the curriculum.
 - The inclusion of environmental, social, cultural, and economic dimensions of sustainability.

- The extent to which the curriculum aligns with the four competence areas of the GreenComp framework:
- The approach involved:
 - searching for keywords that could find direct references sustainability competences and inclusion principles such as “sustainability”, "competence", "inclusion", as well as related keywords such as "responsibility", "participation", "activism", "ethics", "climate change", "equity" etc.,
 - identifying key themes, and mapping curricular elements to the specific GreenComp competence areas
- Data Synthesis and Reporting:
 - Each country’s team synthesized their findings into a structured report, using a common template to ensure consistency.
 - This report included:
 - An overview of the education system.
 - Definitions of sustainability-related terms.
 - Analysis of the curriculum's coverage of sustainability dimensions and GreenComp areas.
 - Information on teacher education, good practices, and identified gaps.

2.2 Comparative Analysis

The compiled report builds on the individual countries’ analyses to identify broader trends and patterns across the participating nations. This involved:

- Cross-Country Mapping:
 - The findings from each country report were systematically compared and contrasted to identify similarities and differences in how curricula address sustainability and align with the GreenComp framework.
 - This involved creating comparative tables and summaries to highlight key variations and commonalities.
- Thematic Synthesis:
 - The analysis focused on synthesizing the findings around key themes, such as:
 - The overall emphasis on sustainability in the curriculum.

- The balance between different dimensions of sustainability.
- The integration of GreenComp competence areas.
- Approaches to teacher education and assessment.
- Identified strengths and gaps in sustainability education.
- Identification of Best Practices and Recommendations:
 - Based on the comparative analysis, the report identifies examples of selected innovative approaches and good practices in sustainability education
 - It also synthesizes recommendations for strengthening sustainability education in curricula and educational policies.

3.3 Methodological Considerations

- Use of GreenComp as a Framework: The GreenComp framework served as a central tool for this study, providing a consistent structure for analyzing and comparing sustainability competences across different educational contexts.
- Qualitative Approach: The study primarily employed a qualitative approach, focusing on the content and framing of sustainability within curricular documents. This allowed for in-depth analysis of educational philosophies, learning objectives, and pedagogical approaches.
- Limitations:
 - This analysis by itself is limited by the content of the official and supportive documents and may not fully capture how sustainability is taught and learned in practice. Follow up reports based on focus group discussions with educators and school teachers along with identified practices based on empirical evidence from schools will be published separately to be used with this mapping study in order to give a complete picture of the status of Education for Sustainable Development in participating countries.
 - Variations in the level of detail and specificity in curricular documents across countries introduced some challenges in comparison.

3. Country-wise analysis of National Core Curricula

This section details each country's analysis of their national core curricula regarding sustainability and Education for Sustainable Development (ESD). Each country's analysis includes:

- An overview of their education system.
- Definitions of key terms ("sustainability," "sustainable development," and "sustainable competence") as defined in their national curricula.
- How their curricula address the four dimensions of sustainability.
- How their curricula address the four GreenComp competence areas
- Whether and how their curricula mention assessment strategies for sustainability competences in schools.
- Examples of good or desirable ESD practices at the primary and secondary school levels.
- Strengths and gaps in their curricula concerning the prioritization, implementation, and development of sustainability competences in learners.

3.1 Bulgaria

3.1.1 Overview of the Education System

In Bulgaria, primary education covers grades 1-7, catering to students aged 7-14. Secondary education includes both lower and upper levels, spanning grades 8-12 and ages 14-18. The National Development Programme BULGARIA 2030 serves as a high-level strategic document that guides development policies across all sectors of public administration, with its philosophy rooted in the UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). The "Education and Skills" priority is fundamental for Bulgaria's development, focusing on areas like inclusive education, teacher prestige, quality of education, lifelong learning, and digitalization. The Preschool and School Education Act defines the main goals of education, including the acquisition of competencies to apply sustainable development principles.

3.1.2 Definitions

Bulgaria's National Development Programme BULGARIA 2030 is a key strategic document that shapes development policies, drawing heavily from the UN Sustainable Development Goals. The "Education and Skills" priority within this program emphasizes the importance of education for Bulgaria's development, with specific goals aligned with the Sustainable Development Goals. The Preschool and School Education Act outlines the main goals of education, including the development of students' competencies to apply sustainable development principles. Ordinance No. 13 defines the concepts of "sustainability,"

“sustainable development,” and “competence for sustainability,” with a focus on environmental education and ecological culture.

In the Bulgarian curriculum, “sustainability” and “sustainable development” are key principles, reflecting a globally accepted understanding of balanced development. These terms are used interchangeably, focusing on long-term environmental preservation, social justice, and economic well-being. While “competence for sustainability” isn't explicitly defined, it's implied through the knowledge, skills, and attitudes students are expected to acquire.

Compared to the GreenComp framework, which provides clearer definitions and a systematic structure, the Bulgarian curriculum integrates these ideas implicitly. GreenComp distinguishes between sustainability and sustainable development, defining sustainability as prioritizing the needs of all life forms within planetary boundaries and outlining sustainability competence as a capability structured into specific competencies.

3.1.3 Four Dimensions of Sustainability

The Bulgarian educational system addresses sustainability in ecological, social, cultural, and economic contexts. Social sustainability is emphasized through inclusion and equal opportunities, supported by legal documents. Cultural sustainability is supported by curricula that preserve national identity and promote intercultural understanding. Economic sustainability is reflected in subjects like geography, civic education, and technology, focusing on global economic processes and the sustainable use of resources, with vocational training aligned with sustainable development.

- **Environmental Sustainability:** Integrated into curricula through environmental education, focusing on ecological culture and behavior to protect nature and create a sustainable environment.
- **Social Sustainability:** Emphasized through inclusion and equal opportunities, addressed in civic education, promoting principles of democracy, human rights, diversity, and solidarity.
- **Cultural Sustainability:** Supported by curricular content that preserves and transmits national identity while promoting intercultural understanding, teaching students to value diversity and respect different cultural communities.
- **Economic Sustainability:** Reflected in subjects like geography, civic education, and technology, where students learn about global economic processes and the sustainable use of resources, with vocational training aligned with sustainable community development.

3.1.4 GreenComp Competence Areas in Bulgarian School Curricula

The Bulgarian curriculum addresses the four competence areas of GreenComp through various subjects and educational practices.

- **Embodying Sustainability Values:** The curriculum fosters awareness of global issues and ethical responsibility related to sustainability through subjects like Man and Society, Geography, and Biology. It conveys moral and civic values, encouraging students to adopt ideals such as human rights, justice, responsibility, and respect. Environmental education promotes a sense of personal responsibility toward nature, and students are encouraged to reflect on their own values and behavior in the context of sustainability.
- **Embracing Complexity:** The curriculum promotes interdisciplinary collaboration and the integration of knowledge to help students understand the complexity of real-world issues. It encourages systems and critical thinking, with foundations laid in primary education through the study of ecosystems and the interactions between social and natural processes.
- **Envisioning Sustainable Futures:** Bulgarian education encourages students' imagination and creativity through activities like drawing, projects, and role-playing games. Various subjects and activities support the development of future-oriented imagination and creative thinking, such as discussions on the UN Sustainable Development Goals and explorations of forecasts and trends in geography and economics classes.
- **Acting for Sustainability:** Students are encouraged to take individual and collective action in support of sustainable development through tasks that apply what they've learned and collective activities like park clean-ups and environmental campaigns. The school environment provides mechanisms for student engagement, such as student councils, where students can exercise collective responsibility and advocacy.

3.1.5 Teacher Education and Leadership Training

In Bulgaria, the legal and strategic frameworks support the education and training of teachers and school leaders in sustainability competences. The Law on Pre-school and School Education includes the development of skills related to sustainable development, and the Strategic Framework for the Development of Education, Training, and Learning (2021-2030) emphasizes sustainability. Teacher education and leadership programs are integrating sustainability themes, but in-service teachers and school leaders still vary in their confidence and readiness to address sustainability challenges. National professional development programs offer courses aligned with Ordinance No. 13 (2016) to promote environmental awareness, healthy lifestyles, and ecological culture.

3.1.6 Assessment of Sustainability Competences

Sustainability is integrated into the general assessment system in Bulgaria, with factual knowledge evaluated through standard forms like tests and projects. Attitudes and skills are monitored through teacher observation and qualitative feedback, with self-assessment and peer assessment used in some cases. Teacher preparation is improving, with growing attention to professional development in sustainability education.

3.1.7 Identified Good Practices

Bulgaria's curricular and policy documents encourage good practices in sustainability education.

- **Integrated Civic, Health, Environmental, and Intercultural Education:** Ordinance № 13/2016 mandates the integration of sustainability-related themes across subjects, allowing teachers flexibility in choosing interdisciplinary approaches and project-based learning. This autonomy enables educators to address local contexts and promote ecological awareness, healthy habits, and democratic participation.
- **Eco-schools Program:** Many Bulgarian schools participate in the Eco-schools program, coordinated by the Foundation for Environmental Education. This program promotes a whole-school approach to sustainability through concrete environmental actions and empowers students to take leadership roles.
- **National Conferences on Sustainability Education:** National conferences advance teacher training and awareness of sustainability topics. These conferences provide platforms for educators and professionals to discuss strategies for integrating sustainability into the curriculum.

3.1.8 Key Strengths and Gaps

The Bulgarian curriculum integrates sustainability principles across various subjects and educational levels. Policy documents emphasize the development of skills and competencies for sustainable development, for example, initiatives like the Eco-schools program and national conferences support sustainability education and teacher training. Moreover, there is a focus on interdisciplinary approaches and project-based learning to address sustainability challenges.

However, Bulgaria still needs to ensure consistent teacher training and support for effective implementation of sustainability education across all school levels. The need for a systematic approach to monitoring and evaluating the outcomes of sustainability education is another

area to be paid attention to. Also, the challenge of providing more practical, hands-on learning experiences, especially in underserved areas, continues.

3.2 Finland

3.2.1 Overview of the Education System

In Finland, education is divided into primary education (grades 1–6, ages 7–12), lower secondary education (grades 7–9, ages 13–15), and upper secondary education (grades 10–12, ages 16–18). All three levels are compulsory and publicly funded. The National Core Curriculum for Basic Education (2014) and the National Core Curriculum for General Upper Secondary Education (2019) provide the framework for educational goals, values, and subject-specific content. The Finnish curricula as well as education system is known for its strong emphasis on student well-being, equity and inclusion, i.e., ensuring appropriate support for all students; and transversal competences consisting of “knowledge, skills, values, attitudes and will” (Finnish National Agency for Education, 2014). The seven interconnected competence areas defined in the National Core Curriculum for Basic Education (2014) are summarized in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Transversal competences in basic education in Finland (Halinen, 2018)

3.2.2 Definitions

The Finnish basic education curriculum defines sustainability primarily through the concept of ecosocial knowledge and ability, emphasizing the importance of climate change awareness and responsible lifestyles. It highlights the need for pupils to develop a sustainable way of life, taking into the ecological, economic, social, and cultural dimensions of sustainability. The curricula do not use the term 'sustainability competence' explicitly, however, the Basic Education Curriculum (2014) includes transversal competence area T7—**Participation, involvement and building a sustainable future**—which closely aligns with GreenComp’s definition of sustainability competence.

In connection to the GreenComp framework, the curriculum strongly supports values of environmental awareness, ethical responsibility, and active citizenship, particularly at the basic education level. While the upper secondary curriculum mentions sustainability less frequently, it incorporates related values across various subjects, especially in ethics and social studies, which are outlined in the following subsections.

3.2.3 Four Dimensions of Sustainability

The Finnish basic education curriculum (EDUFI, 2014) covers environmental, economic, social, and cultural sustainability across all education levels found under the framework of ecosocial knowledge and ability (p. 26). At upper secondary level (EUFI, 2019), students engage with ecological responsibility, economic literacy, cultural understanding, and social justice, supported by multidisciplinary learning modules stated in the individual subject goals:

- Environmental sustainability: Integrated into science, geography, and environmental studies; supported by project-based learning and real-life applications.
- Social sustainability: Promoted mostly through democratic participation, equity, and inclusion, especially visible in school culture and student welfare systems.
- Cultural sustainability: Reflected in language awareness, arts, and fostering respect for diversity.
- Economic sustainability: Taught within social studies and ethics, encouraging students to analyze sustainability in economic policies and systems.

In addition, “equity, gender equality, democracy, and well-being” (EDUFI, 2019, p.13) are emphasized as underlying values of the curriculum itself. Inclusion, equity, and social cohesion are strongly promoted in the implementation of student welfare systems, with participation and voice of students being at the centre.

3.2.4 GreenComp competence areas in Finnish School Curricula

- **Embodying Sustainability Values:** Students are encouraged to develop responsibility, care, and respect for people and nature. Civic participation and ethical reflection are integrated across subjects. Both basic and upper secondary curricula foster awareness of sustainability as a core value, deeply embedded in school culture and transversal competences. In the basic education curriculum, values such as human dignity, equality, democracy, cultural diversity, and environmental responsibility form the foundation of school education. Students are encouraged to reflect on their roles as responsible individuals and global citizens. Upper secondary education further builds on these by integrating ethical reflection and promoting students' capacity to act with fairness and empathy. Subjects such as ethics, philosophy, social studies, and religion support students in examining their own values and ethical dimensions of sustainability. Students are guided to see themselves as part of the ecosystem and society, and to critically assess how values influence decision-making.
- **Embracing Complexity:** Systems thinking is introduced through multidisciplinary learning modules and problem-based approaches addressing real-world challenges. The curricula promote interdisciplinary and systems thinking through transversal competence areas like "T1 Thinking and learning to learn" and "T7 Participation, involvement and building a sustainable future" in the basic education curriculum (EDUFI, 2014) and subject integration in both curricula. In basic education, sustainability is addressed not just through science and geography, but also through social studies, arts, crafts, and physical education, encouraging learners to see connections between environmental, social, economic, and cultural dimensions. Upper secondary education requires students to integrate knowledge across disciplines and think critically about global challenges such as climate change, inequality, and biodiversity loss. For example, systems thinking is visible in the curriculum's emphasis on understanding the interactions between ecological and social systems, as well as in problem-solving activities that span multiple subjects
- **Envisioning Sustainable Futures:** Creativity, innovation, and imagining future solutions are promoted through project work and student-led initiatives. In basic education, students are supported in imagining a better future through future-oriented activities in environmental studies, art, and civic education. Transversal competences, like T2 "Cultural competence, interaction and expression" (EDUFI, 2014) also promote imaginative engagement and personal expression. In upper secondary education, futures thinking is more explicitly nurtured. Students are encouraged to understand social and ecological trajectories and explore potential solutions to societal challenges. Subjects such as philosophy, geography, and social studies support exploratory thinking and future scenario analysis. The aim is to foster learners' futures literacy—the ability to imagine alternative possibilities and plan toward preferred futures

- **Acting for Sustainability:** Students are involved in practical activities such as eco-projects, democratic school governance, and community outreach, developing agency and responsibility. The Finnish curricula are particularly strong in promoting student agency, action competence, and democratic participation. In basic education, students are encouraged to take part in local projects, community engagement, and environmental activities, often embedded in school routines. The curriculum emphasises both individual responsibility and collective action as means to foster a sustainable future. Research on action competence in Finnish teacher education is still incomplete, but a national survey (n=940) reveals that it mainly influences individual behaviours, not collective actions, and high knowledge levels do not always result in increased action (Oinonen et al., 2024). This highlights the challenge of translating knowledge into collective action in educational practice. Upper secondary curriculum emphasizes civic competence and political agency, students are guided to critically engage with sustainability issues, participate in democratic processes, and hold decision-makers accountable. The upper secondary curriculum mentions responsibility towards their own learning and work (pp. 218, 225, 235), towards health and safety of oneself and others (pp. 233, 321) as well as ethical and social responsibilities as national and global citizens (pp. 116, 135, 265, 310), participation and sense of community (in the context of student welfare), activism, and entrepreneurship (mostly in connection to working life skills and economics)—providing pathways for students to act as change-makers within and beyond school.

To assess these competences, schools use diverse methods, including self-assessment, peer assessment, and portfolio work, but no national tool explicitly assesses sustainability competences.

3.2.5 Teacher Education and Leadership Training

Teacher education programs in Finland include sustainability as part of transversal competence development. Universities and teacher training institutions provide modules on environmental education, global citizenship, and sustainable pedagogy. School leaders receive training on sustainable school management, promoting whole-school approaches and teacher collaboration.

3.2.6 Assessment of sustainability competences

Finnish curricula in basic and upper secondary education indirectly support the evaluation of sustainability competences through formative, holistic, and competence-based assessment embedded within subject learning objectives and general competences. Basic education focuses on supporting learning and encouraging pupil agency in sustainability education through authentic tasks assessing transversal competences. Upper secondary education emphasizes self-assessment and diverse methods like portfolios in subjects related to sustainability. While national curricula lack specific tools for sustainability competence

assessment, teacher autonomy is promoted, and teacher education includes sustainability themes, though specific assessment guidance is limited, leading to varied implementation.

3.2.7 Identified Good Practices

- **Project-based learning in Finnish schools** often centers on real-world environmental issues, allowing students to delve deeply into specific topics like climate change or biodiversity loss. Through research, collaboration, and problem-solving, students gain a comprehensive understanding and develop critical thinking skills related to sustainability.
- **Experiential learning**, such as regular nature walks and outdoor activities, provides students with firsthand experiences in natural environments. These direct interactions foster a deeper appreciation for nature and ecological processes, making abstract concepts more tangible and impactful.
- **Student-led initiatives** play a significant role in promoting environmental awareness and action within Finnish schools. Students often take the lead in organizing recycling campaigns, energy conservation efforts, and other projects that contribute to a more sustainable school environment.
- **Comprehensive waste separation and composting systems** are integral parts of daily life in Finnish schools. Students learn the importance of reducing waste and properly sorting materials for recycling and composting, contributing to a circular economy and minimizing environmental impact.
- Finnish schools actively implement **energy-efficient practices**, such as optimizing lighting and heating, and increasingly adopt renewable energy sources like solar panels. These efforts reduce the schools' carbon footprint and serve as practical examples of sustainable energy use for students.
- The encouragement of **green transportation**, such as walking, cycling, and using public transport, is a key aspect of promoting sustainability. Schools often implement initiatives to support and incentivize these modes of transport, reducing reliance on private vehicles and associated emissions.
- **Phenomenon-based learning** connects real-world environmental problems and other complex issues to the school curriculum in an interdisciplinary manner. This approach encourages students to explore the underlying causes and potential

solutions to these problems, fostering a deeper and more relevant understanding of sustainability.

3.2.8 Key strengths and gaps

As its strengths, Finland's curriculum emphasizes student well-being, equity, and inclusion, and it promotes transversal competences that include knowledge, skills, values, attitudes, and will. The curriculum clearly defines sustainability through ecosocial knowledge and ability, highlighting ecological, economic, social, and cultural dimensions. It incorporates GreenComp competence areas, like Embodying Sustainability Values, Embracing Complexity, Envisioning Sustainable Futures, and Acting for Sustainability, through multidisciplinary learning, project work, and student-led initiatives. The curriculum also promotes student agency and democratic participation, involving students in practical activities like eco-projects and community outreach. Teacher education programs include sustainability, supporting teachers in implementing these concepts.

Despite its strengths, minor gaps can be identified in the Finnish curricula. While it indirectly supports assessing sustainability competences through various methods like self-assessment and portfolio work, it lacks a national tool for explicitly evaluating these competences. Teacher education includes sustainability themes, but specific assessment guidance is limited, leading to varied implementation. Research suggests that action competence often influences individual behaviors rather than collective actions, and high knowledge levels do not always translate to increased action. The upper secondary curriculum mentions sustainability less frequently compared to the basic education curriculum, and translating knowledge into collective action in educational practice remains a challenge.

3.3 Greece

3.3.1 Overview of the Education System

In Greece, education is divided into primary and secondary levels. Primary education includes grades 1-6 for ages 6-12. Secondary education is further divided into Gymnasium (lower secondary) and Lyceum (upper secondary), covering grades 7-12. There are separate curricula guidelines for primary and secondary education in Greece. The core principles of the Greek educational system emphasize a unified, interdisciplinary approach that is inclusive, human-centered, and focused on civic engagement. Learning is organized around key areas such as environment, society, arts, technology, history, natural sciences, literature, and literacy. Sustainability, resilience, and inclusion are common themes throughout these fields.

3.3.2 Definitions

In Greece, the educational community uses and combines concepts like sustainability, environmental awareness, interdisciplinary development, environmental ethics, resilient society, and democracy. These concepts are integrated into modern educational theory and align with European policy. The Greek educational system aims for a unified and interdisciplinary approach, emphasizing inclusion, a human-centered focus, and civic responsibility. Sustainability, resilience, and inclusive discourse serve as a common frame of reference across different fields.

Specifically, the Active Citizen Actions curriculum is a priority, based on the 17 Sustainable Development Goals. For Greece, sustainability involves environmental responsibility and developing skills to manage resources. The Greek curriculum emphasizes developing critical thinking, intergenerational approaches, and visioning, breaking down sustainability into thematic pillars within various subjects. The core principles of the new curricula—citizenship, sustainability, and inclusion—align with GreenComp's definitions.

The Greek educational context frames sustainability and sustainable development as interdisciplinary and value-based, incorporating environmental, social, cultural, and economic dimensions. There's an emphasis on Education for Sustainable Development (ESD) across subjects like geography, environmental studies, citizenship education, and natural sciences. The focus includes understanding the interconnectedness of natural and human systems, promoting critical thinking, ethical responsibility, and active citizenship, and encouraging action-oriented learning for sustainability in daily life. This aligns with the UNESCO ESD framework and covers topics like climate change, biodiversity, inequality, responsible consumption, and democratic participation.

While not always explicitly termed "sustainable competence," the curriculum develops key competencies for sustainability, such as systems thinking, empathy, collaboration, critical reflection, future thinking, and civic engagement. These are integrated into interdisciplinary projects, environmental education, and project-based learning.

3.3.3 Four Dimensions of Sustainability

The contemporary Greek curricula include the skills, resources, and objectives of sustainable development. Sustainability includes social, cultural, economic, and environmental aspects, integrated into various themes and subjects. The Greek curriculum addresses environmental, social, cultural, and economic sustainability through civic education, language, history, and project-based learning. Inclusion and social sustainability are emphasized in middle and upper levels (Gymnasium and Lyceum), focusing on critical thinking, rights, and civic engagement.

- **Environmental Sustainability:** Strongly emphasized in Primary Education through Environmental Studies and Natural Sciences, covering ecosystems, biodiversity, pollution, climate change, recycling, and sustainable living. It is taught through experiential, project-based learning, outdoor education, and eco-school projects.
- **Social Sustainability:** Integrated through themes of human rights, equality, diversity, inclusion, democratic participation, and peace education in subjects like Social & Civic Education, Religious Education, Language and Literature, and Health Education programs. It also appears in cross-curricular thematic frameworks and interdisciplinary projects, such as those addressing diversity, migration, and bullying prevention.
- **Cultural Sustainability:** Promoted through Language and Literature (diverse narratives, oral traditions), History (cultural heritage and identity), Arts (visual arts, music, theater), and Religious Education (intercultural dialogue), encouraging intercultural understanding, cultural heritage preservation, and respect for diverse traditions.
- **Economic Sustainability:** Introduced more explicitly in Secondary Education, especially in Home Economics, Civic and Social Education, and elective projects or environmental education programs, covering responsible consumption, circular economy, personal finance, budgeting, fair trade, and labor rights.

Inclusion and social sustainability are particularly emphasized in Civic and Social Education (Gymnasium), Language and Literature, Religious Education, Health and Sexual Education Programs, and Interdisciplinary Projects. These areas address democracy, justice, equality, diversity, citizen responsibilities, social cohesion, solidarity, non-discrimination, empathy, social awareness, and gender equality. Primary school introduces empathy, environmental care, and cooperation, while lower secondary focuses more on rights, social justice, and active citizenship. Upper secondary discusses global issues, inequality, climate justice, and economic systems.

3.3.4 GreenComp Competence Areas in Greek School Curricula

The Greek national curriculum, developed by the Institute of Educational Policy (IEΠ), aligns with the EU's GreenComp framework by embedding sustainability principles across educational levels. It incorporates the four GreenComp competence areas: Embodying Sustainability Values, Embracing Complexity in Sustainability, Envisioning Sustainable Futures, and Acting for Sustainability, through interdisciplinary approaches and thematic units. The curriculum emphasizes environmental education and sustainable development, fostering values like empathy, responsibility, and care for the planet. It encourages systems thinking and critical analysis of environmental and social issues and involves students in envisioning sustainable futures through project-based learning and scenario planning.

Additionally, it promotes active citizenship through community projects and decision-making, reflecting the competence of acting for sustainability.

- **Embodying Sustainability Values:** The Greek national curriculum integrates sustainability as a core value, aligned with Education for Sustainable Development (ESD) principles and the UN SDGs. It fosters awareness and ethical responsibility by emphasizing respect for human rights, justice, peace, biodiversity, and intercultural understanding across subjects. Students are encouraged to reflect on personal values and develop a sense of responsibility through activities like storytelling, ethical dilemmas, group discussions, and community projects. Social sustainability is nurtured through teaching inclusion, equity, and diversity, promoting non-discrimination, gender equality, and human rights education.
- **Embracing Complexity:** The Greek national curriculum addresses the complexity and interconnectedness of sustainability issues through interdisciplinary and project-based learning. Students explore how environmental, social, cultural, and economic issues are interrelated, developing systems and critical thinking. They analyze real-world scenarios and engage in problem-solving, group debates, and community mapping to understand sustainability from various perspectives. As students advance, they examine more nuanced issues like economic inequality, global health, and environmental justice.
- **Envisioning Sustainable Futures:** The curriculum encourages students to envision alternative futures and consider the long-term consequences of actions through creative, exploratory, and participatory activities. While not explicitly using the term "futures literacy," it fosters this concept through project-based learning, language and literature, and civic education. Students imagine sustainable worlds, explore global challenges, and design action plans, developing imagination, creativity, and adaptability.
- **Acting for Sustainability:** The curriculum emphasizes student agency and participation, encouraging engagement with sustainability challenges locally and globally through interdisciplinary projects, Environmental Education Programs, and thematic weeks. Students take initiative, collaborate, and act to promote environmental protection, inclusion, and social justice. They are encouraged to understand citizenship, institutions, and democratic participation, fostering critical dialogue and problem-solving.

3.3.5 Teacher Education and Leadership Training

Education for sustainable development (ESD) and sustainability competences are gaining attention in Greece, aligned with international and EU frameworks. Sustainability is embedded in the National Strategic Framework for ESD, and the Ministry of Education

supports teacher training through Environmental Education Centers (ΚΠΕ). Universities include sustainability in education degrees, with courses like "Environmental Education" and "Education for Sustainable Development," though these are often elective. In-service training is provided through Regional Training Centers (PEKES) and ΚΠΕ, focusing on practical tools, project-based learning, and community engagement. School leadership training is less formalized but sometimes includes modules on inclusive education and school-community partnerships. Challenges include the lack of systematic integration of sustainability, its project-based nature, and the need for capacity building and consistent assessment frameworks.

In-service teachers and school leaders in Greece generally have moderate awareness but limited confidence and preparedness to address sustainability challenges comprehensively. They understand basic concepts like environmental protection but lack a deeper understanding of systemic challenges. Confidence in teaching sustainability in an interdisciplinary way is low, and many teachers need more structured training and tools.

3.3.6 Assessment of Sustainability Competences

Assessment focuses on formative, process-oriented evaluation within project-based and interdisciplinary learning, emphasizing engagement, ethical awareness, collaboration, and real-world action over formal grading. Qualitative and participatory methods like reflective practices, student journals, group discussions, peer feedback, and presentations are used. Teachers design their own rubrics and indicators, drawing from ESD guidelines, to assess critical thinking, civic responsibility, ethical reasoning, and the ability to propose sustainable solutions. Teacher education emphasizes building educators' capacity for holistic assessment, using tools like project rubrics, narrative evaluation, and portfolios. There is no standardized national toolkit, but discussions are ongoing to develop such tools, especially for integrating the GreenComp framework.

3.3.7 Identified Good Practices

Greece's curricular and policy documents encourage several good practices in sustainability education, focusing on environmental sustainability and related enablers like teacher autonomy, collaboration, and inclusion.

- **Curricular Frameworks and Educational Guidelines:** Revised national curricula emphasize interdisciplinary and project-based learning, especially in primary education, exploring real-life issues like climate change, inequality, consumption, and civic responsibility. "Thematic Weeks" at the secondary level embed sustainability in a cross-curricular format, and Skills Workshops, mandatory since 2021, promote critical thinking, creativity, collaboration, and real-world engagement across primary and lower secondary schools, using UN SDGs as framing tools.

- **Policy and Institutional Support:** The National Strategy for Education for Sustainable Development aligns with UNESCO's 2030 goals, promoting a whole-school approach that integrates learning content, school culture, infrastructure, and community partnerships. It encourages democratic school governance, student participation, and ecological footprints for schools, supported by European exchanges and e-Twinning programs. The Institute of Educational Policy (IEΠ) provides teacher toolkits and encourages teacher autonomy and inclusive pedagogies. Collaboration with civil society and international networks, such as UNESCO Associated Schools Project Network (ASPnet) and Eco-Schools, fosters innovation through peer exchange, whole-school initiatives, and community projects.

Examples of good practices include school gardens and composting projects, student climate action campaigns, interdisciplinary SDG mapping projects, co-teaching and teacher learning communities focused on sustainability, inclusive sustainability storytelling, and sociocultural events that promote multilingualism and open learning in nature.

Greece's educational policy and curricular framework support sustainability education through integrated programs, institutional guidelines, and enablers like teacher autonomy, collaboration, and inclusion, shifting from isolated environmental content toward competence-based, participatory, and socially aware education.

3.3.8 Key Strengths and Gaps

The Greek curriculum integrates sustainability across various subjects, emphasizing interdisciplinary and project-based learning. There is a strong focus on developing skills such as critical thinking, creativity, and collaboration, alongside knowledge acquisition. Policy documents and frameworks promote a whole-school approach to ESD, encouraging student participation and community engagement. Initiatives like the Skills Workshops and Thematic Weeks provide structured ways to incorporate sustainability into the curriculum. Teacher autonomy and the availability of resources from institutions like the IEP support the implementation of sustainability education.

However, there can be a tension between exam-centered curricula and the need for more experiential, outdoor learning. Despite policy efforts, there may be challenges in fully integrating sustainability into the daily life and structure of schools. There's a risk of schools becoming too focused on formal education, potentially neglecting non-formal, informal, and nature-based learning.

3.4 Hungary

3.4.1 Overview of the Education System

In Hungary, primary education encompasses preschool education from ages 3 to 6, and primary school that includes grades 1 to 8, typically for students aged 6 to 14. Secondary education then follows with general and vocational tracks, covering ages 14 to 18 or 19. Education is mandatory from ages 3 to 16. Hungary's education policy emphasizes inclusive and equitable access to quality education, with targeted support for disadvantaged and marginalized groups. Sustainability is integrated into the Hungarian National Core Curriculum (NCC).

3.4.2 Definitions

In Hungary's core curriculum, "sustainability" is defined as the state and process of environmental, social, and economic aspects existing in a harmonious interconnectedness. This definition aims to achieve a balance where current development actions do not compromise the needs and resources available for future generations. The curriculum emphasizes that sustainable development is a complex and dynamic process of social development. This process seeks to balance the health of the environment, social equity, and economic factors. The ultimate goal is to secure human prosperity and the ongoing conservation of ecological resources.

Compared to the GreenComp framework, Hungary's curriculum has distinctive features. While it includes individual skills and knowledge, it simultaneously highlights the importance of collaboration, collective actions, and the potential for individuals to influence and drive change in society towards a more sustainable future.

3.4.3 Four Dimensions of Sustainability

The Hungarian curriculum integrates the concepts of environmental, social, and economic sustainability. While cultural sustainability is embedded within the social dimension, the curriculum emphasizes the interconnectedness of all four dimensions.

- **Environmental Sustainability:** This is a key component, referred to as the "soundness of the environment." The curriculum stresses the importance of maintaining a healthy environment for current and future generations.
- **Social Sustainability:** This is a major focus, driven by geopolitical codes of vision theory, geopolitics of education, and integrated education policies. The curriculum actively promotes social justice, equity, and the development of active and engaged citizens. It explicitly mentions the development of students' skills to foster social inclusion.

- **Economic Sustainability:** The curriculum integrates economic sustainability by seeking a balance between economic factors, environmental soundness, and social equity. It recognizes that a sustainable economy is essential for human prosperity and the conservation of ecological wealth.
- **Cultural Sustainability:** While not always explicitly separated, cultural sustainability is interwoven within the curriculum's broader emphasis on social development, equity, and inclusion. The promotion of intercultural understanding and respect for diversity contributes to cultural sustainability.

3.4.4 GreenComp Competence Areas in Hungarian School Curricula

The Hungarian curriculum addresses the four competence areas of the GreenComp framework, although it may express them through its own terminology and pedagogical approaches.

Embodying Sustainability Values: The curriculum is an ethical and value-based framework embedding sustainability, emphasizing students' duty and promoting respect for nature, social responsibility, and empathy. Sustainability guides behavior and decision-making. Based on active citizenship, it instills social responsibility and includes the study of democracy, fostering participation and community building. Inclusivity, equal opportunities, and respect are promoted, considering social equity, diversity, and inclusion integral to sustainable development. Practical projects encourage reflection on choices and their sustainability effects, stressing critical thinking about values and behaviors. Activity-based guidance integrates sustainability into daily life, encouraging lifelong habits.

Embracing Complexity: The Hungarian curriculum emphasizes the interdisciplinarity of sustainability, allowing for cooperation across various subject areas. The curriculum suggests that educators incorporate themes of sustainability into different subjects, encouraging a comprehensive consideration of sustainability issues across disciplines. This interdisciplinary cooperation aims to provide students with a well-rounded understanding and the capabilities to solve complex sustainability problems in their daily lives. Systems thinking and critical thinking are explicitly promoted in the curriculum as meta-competencies necessary for making sense of complex sustainability issues. The integrated, systemic approach to sustainability is reinforced by urging students to explore the links between ecological, social, economic, and cultural dimensions. The curriculum fosters critical thinking by engaging students in activities that require them to address sustainability practices critically, contemplate the ethics of their own and others' actions, be aware of their positions within larger systems, and consider the consequences of their actions. Interdisciplinary education encourages students to develop an awareness of and address other global challenges, such as biodiversity loss, inequality, sustainable resource management, and climate change.

Envisioning Sustainable Futures: The Hungarian curriculum encourages students to use imagination to explore the possibilities of sustainability and envision what sustainable scenarios might look like. This approach aims to foster innovative thinking and creative problem-solving as students work with projects and learning experiences that require them to visualize implementable, sustainable solutions to real-life issues. The curriculum specifically supports the development of systems thinking and futures literacy. For example, students explore the intricately knotted and overlapping aspects of sustainability challenges, helping them learn to respond to new conditions and unknowns. These competencies equip students to proactively and innovatively tackle the challenges of the future. Beyond promoting environmentally responsible behaviors, the educational objectives aim to enhance creative and critical thinking, a sense of responsibility and involvement in the community, and the development of skills for managing environmental conflicts. Graduates are expected to receive guidance on how socio-economic modernization impacts local ecosystems in practice and how environmental resources influence each other, as well as learning about sustainable consumption principles. However, it has been noted that while the cultivation of sustainable behavior should be a main goal, supported by the necessary knowledge, skills, and competencies, national curricula often do not focus enough on the explicit development of sustainable behavior.

Acting for Sustainability: The curriculum provides teaching steps to encourage self and team action in pursuing sustainability initiatives. Students are invited to actively engage with sustainability by undertaking projects, getting involved in the community, and taking ownership of their immediate and wider social and environmental context. While the term "action competence" is not directly mentioned, the curriculum supports the development of action-oriented competencies aligned with this concept, such as critical thinking, problem-solving, and decision-making skills, and the capacity to act individually and together in sustainability contexts. Student-based and independent forms of learning promote student independence, involvement, and inspiration to lead and participate in sustainability activities, touching on initiation skills and agency. The curriculum also places a strong emphasis on developing political will and civic participation among students. It foregrounds democratic participation, critical inquiry into social issues, and accountability. Students are empowered not only to comprehend sustainability issues but also to exercise their rights and responsibilities to hold organizations and authority figures accountable for sustainable habits, standards, and policies. Civic skills are emphasized as essential for students to engage with each other in political and social ways that build a sustainable society.

3.4.5 Teacher Education and Leadership Training

In Hungary, the integration of sustainability competences into teacher education and school leader training programs is occurring gradually. However, it is not yet fully systematized or

universally applied across all programs. Sustainability education is primarily found in specialized courses within teacher training, environmental education, and leadership preparation programs. These programs focus on developing skills that enable teachers to better incorporate sustainability into their teaching practices and school management approaches.

Despite educators' general understanding of the importance of sustainability-related knowledge and skills, many still express a need for more effective pedagogical approaches and specific contexts for implementation. They believe that professional development should place a greater emphasis on sustainable development education. National professional development programs for trainers in Hungary are beginning to incorporate explicit elements of sustainability within their respective themes, aiming to enhance educators' capacity in this area.

3.4.6 Identified Good Practices

The curricular and other education policy/research documents in Hungary encourage several good practices in sustainability education:

- **Eco-school Program (Ökoiskola Program):** Schools certified as "Eco-schools" systematically integrate sustainability into their educational approach and operations. This integration promotes environmental awareness, social inclusion, and community collaboration through a whole-institution approach. (More information: [Link to Eco-school Program]) official site of Eco-school program, only in Hungarian: - [LINK](#))
- **Green Kindergarten Program (Zöld Óvoda Program):** This initiative fosters environmental and social sustainability in early childhood education. It emphasizes outdoor education, experiential learning, and the development of environmentally conscious behaviors among the youngest learners. (More details: [Link](#) to Green Kindergarten Program, only in Hungarian])
- **Forest School Program (Erdei Iskola Program):** This program encourages project-based, experiential education in natural settings. It promotes teacher collaboration and autonomy by allowing educators to design interdisciplinary outdoor learning activities focused on sustainability. (Further information: [[Link](#) to Forest School Program] only in Hungarian)
- **Local Environmental and Health Education Programs (Környezeti és egészségnevelési program):** These programs are mandatory in all Hungarian educational institutions. They are designed locally to ensure that sustainability topics (environmental, social, and economic) are embedded within the school's daily activities. These programs enhance teachers' autonomy and encourage inclusive and collaborative learning approaches.

3.4.7 Key Strengths and Gaps

The curriculum defines sustainability in a comprehensive way, emphasizing the interconnectedness of environmental, social, and economic factors. It integrates sustainability principles across various subjects and educational levels and promotes the development of key competencies like systems thinking, critical thinking, and action-oriented skills. At the same time, it encourages innovative teaching approaches, including project-based learning and community engagement. There are several good practices in place, such as the Eco-school and Forest School programs, that support sustainability education.

In terms of gaps, a lack of practical training and professional development opportunities for educators in sustainability education stands out. Insufficient operationalization of sustainability concepts in teacher training, leading to a lack of concrete tools and strategies for teachers is also something to be paid attention to. In addition, the absence of standardized national assessment frameworks designed around sustainability competences, like in many other countries, creates gaps in accountability.

3.4.8. The importance of climate change as a societal problem

In Hungary, climate change is formally acknowledged in the National Core Curriculum as an interdisciplinary issue affecting environmental, economic, and social systems. However, societal attitudes towards climate change and sustainability are regionally diverse, as evidenced by the Climate Change Attitude Index developed within the National Adaptation Geo-information System (NATÉR). This index, based on representative public surveys across Hungarian counties, classifies regions into four categories depending on how favourable local public attitudes are towards climate change adaptation and environmental responsibility.

The data show considerable territorial disparities. As Figure 3 emphasizes, while some counties demonstrate a readiness above the national average suggesting higher public awareness, willingness to cooperate, and openness to adapt, others fall significantly below. The index highlights regions where decision-makers can expect greater support for climate adaptation measures, and conversely, areas where social vulnerability and scepticism may hinder effective policy implementation. These variations often correlate with socioeconomic deprivation, suggesting that climate change is not only an environmental issue, but also deeply intertwined with social justice, as well as awareness raising. For example, initiatives like the European Researchers' Night can support awareness-raising efforts in rural areas, helping to bridge regional disparities in climate change perception. Fortunately, the Hungarian researcher's Night has a real and strong potential as one of the hugest science festival night in the EU (Merza et al, 2024). NATÉR's soft data underline that climate adaptation is not only a technical or policy challenge but requires shifting mindsets and

engaging communities. Where environmental awareness is low, particularly in rural or economically disadvantaged areas, climate change tends to be deprioritised in favour of more immediate social or financial concerns. Therefore, educational responses especially in formal curricula must go beyond knowledge transmission and foster critical thinking, empathy, and civic engagement to enhance collective resilience.

Figure 3: Adaptation - Public Climate Change Attitudes Index, source: NATÉR (dark orange: Attitude much more favourable than the national average. light yellow: Attitude less favourable than the national average)

Interestingly, the NATÉR 2015 map titled “Climate Change as a Societal Problem” reveals a somewhat different pattern compared to other climate attitude indicators. Figure 3 illustrates how climate change is prioritised relative to other societal issues across Hungary's counties, with results expressed in comparison to the national average. The data indicate that in several counties across Transdanubia such as Győr-Moson-Sopron, Vas, Baranya, and Tolna residents ranked climate change as a more important issue than the national average. In contrast, counties like Borsod-Abaúj-Zemplén, Szabolcs-Szatmár-Bereg, and Pest megye placed less emphasis on it. These regional variations suggest that public perceptions of climate change are shaped not only by environmental exposure but also by socio-economic and cultural contexts. The relative importance attributed to climate change as a societal problem can influence how receptive communities are to adaptation policies. Thus, recognising these geographic disparities is essential for designing targeted educational and communication strategies that foster sustainability competences and align with the GreenComp framework’s emphasis on political agency and systems thinking.

Figure 4: Adaptation - The importance of climate change as a societal issue, source: NATÉR (dark yellow: climate change prioritised above the national average Light yellow: Climate change ranked lower than the national average).

These insights are crucial for the project and this report, as they help contextualise sustainability education within regional social attitudes, enabling more effective, locally tailored curriculum development and policy recommendations.

3.5 Portugal

3.5.1 Overview of the Education System

In Portugal, primary education spans grades 1 to 6, catering to students aged 6 to 11 years old. Secondary education covers grades 7 to 12, for students aged 12 to 18 years old. Portugal's educational policies prioritize ensuring equity in access to education for all students, with specific programs designed to support marginalized groups and provide equal educational opportunities. Environmental education is a core component of the curriculum across all school levels, with initiatives like the Eco-Schools program promoting environmental awareness and active student participation in sustainability projects.

3.5.2 Definitions

The core curriculum in Portugal defines key terms related to sustainability as follows:

- “Sustentabilidade/Sustainability”: The preservation of the environment, ensuring its protection for future generations.
- “Desenvolvimento sustentável/Sustainable development”: A development model focused on meeting the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs[cite: 19, 20].
- “Competências de sustentabilidade/Sustainable competence”: A set of knowledge, skills, and attitudes that foster responsible and empathetic behaviors towards the planet.

These definitions align with the broader understanding of sustainability and sustainable development, emphasising the importance of environmental preservation and intergenerational responsibility. Compared to the GreenComp framework, there are differences in how sustainability competence is defined. While the Portuguese definition emphasizes responsible and empathetic attitudes, GreenComp also highlights the ability to embrace complex systems and take action for ecosystem health and justice.

3.5.3 Four Dimensions of Sustainability

The Portuguese curriculum addresses the concepts of social, cultural, and economic sustainability in addition to environmental sustainability.

- **Environmental Sustainability:** This is a core aspect of the curriculum, promoted through programs like Eco-Schools, which encourage environmental awareness and student participation in sustainability projects.
- **Social Sustainability:** Emphasized through concepts such as democratic participation and social justice, which are central to the curriculum. The curriculum also incorporates policies aimed at ensuring equity in access to education for all students, including marginalized groups.
- **Cultural Sustainability:** Closely tied to social sustainability, cultural awareness and intercultural dialogue are promoted within the curriculum.
- **Economic Sustainability:** While less explicitly addressed, economic sustainability is covered indirectly through topics like responsible consumption and economic literacy, often within interdisciplinary projects.

The curriculum integrates these dimensions to provide a holistic understanding of sustainability, particularly in lower and upper secondary education.

3.5.4 GreenComp Competence Areas in Portuguese School Curricula

The Portuguese curriculum addresses the four competence areas of the GreenComp framework:

- **Embodying Sustainability Values:** The curriculum promotes these values through the “Education for Citizenship” framework, encouraging ethical and responsible behavior towards the environment and society. It fosters social sustainability through discussions on social justice, cultural awareness, and human rights, and encourages students to reflect on their personal values and roles as active, responsible citizens.
- **Embracing Complexity:** The curriculum supports interdisciplinary collaboration and systems thinking through subjects like Geography, Natural Sciences, and Environmental Education. Students analyze complex socio-environmental issues, developing critical thinking and an understanding of interconnected systems, aligning with GreenComp’s emphasis on embracing complexity.
- **Envisioning Sustainable Futures:** The curriculum encourages students to envision sustainable futures through creativity, problem-solving, and project-based learning. Interdisciplinary projects prompt students to imagine alternative futures and develop innovative solutions to contemporary challenges, fostering futures literacy and adaptability.
- **Acting for Sustainability:** The curriculum promotes student agency through participatory projects, especially in Environmental Education and Citizenship Education. Students are encouraged to initiate and participate in collective actions, such as school-wide sustainability projects and community engagement, and to engage in political participation and advocacy to act for sustainability at various levels.

3.5.5 Teacher Education and Leadership Training

Continuous teacher training in Portugal addresses the need to update educational practices to respond to evolving economic, social, technical, and cultural contexts, with the goal of equipping teachers to effectively integrate sustainability into their teaching. Teacher education programs provide opportunities for reflection and curriculum adaptation to address sustainability-related challenges. Several training programs focus on sustainability:

- Sustainable Landscape and Architecture Program: Certified training for upper primary and secondary education teachers.
- “Sustainable Development as a Domain of Citizenship Education”: A workshop to raise teachers' awareness of development issues and inequalities.

- Education for Sustainable Development – Environment, Economy, and Culture in Curricular Flexibility Projects: A course for teachers from all recruitment groups in basic and secondary education.
- Development Education Framework: Articulation with the Citizenship and Development Curriculum Component: Training to promote Sustainable Development within Citizenship Education.

3.5.6 Assessment of Sustainability Competences

The Portuguese curriculum does not provide explicit tools or metrics for assessing sustainability competencies. Instead, assessment is generally integrated into broader evaluations of civic participation, critical thinking, and problem-solving skills. While these skills align with GreenComp's framework, there is a lack of structured evaluation methods specifically designed for sustainability competencies.

3.5.7 Identified Good Practices

Portugal's educational framework encourages several good practices in sustainability education:

- **The Eco-Schools project** is a key initiative, promoting environmental education and sustainability through school-wide involvement in sustainable actions and practical learning experiences.
- Various projects for the 2024-2025 academic year offer diverse opportunities for schools to engage with sustainability, including: **Blue Challenge 2025, A Biodiversidade da Minha Escola, Eco-Pátios, Hortas Bio nas Eco-Escolas, Eco-Trilhos, O Mar Começa Aqui , Rota Concelhia de Ação pelo Clima (Rota Concelhia), O Ar que Eu Respiro, Muros com Vida, Brigada #MARVIVO (Brigada #AMARoMAR), Recreios com Vida , Leva a tua Turma ao Oceanário (Desafio Oceanário) and FoodEducators**
- Several alternative schools and methodologies in Portugal focus on sustainability, such as Escola Básica do Falcão (Porto), Vila-Escola Sustentável, Escola da Ponte (O Porto), Escola Montessori do Porto, Tamera (Odemira, Alentejo) and Santana Madeira Biosphere.

3.5.8 Key Strengths and Gaps

The Portuguese curriculum integrates sustainability concepts across different dimensions (environmental, social, cultural). There is a strong emphasis on environmental education, with initiatives like the Eco-Schools program. Within the social sustainability framework, the curriculum promotes active citizenship and social justice. In addition, teacher training

programs, unlike many other countries, are increasingly focused on equipping teachers to integrate sustainability into their practices.

Still, there is a lack of explicit tools and metrics for assessing sustainability competencies. While systems thinking and interdisciplinary collaboration are encouraged, they are not structurally integrated into the curriculum. Competences around the future, especially "futures literacy" can be emphasized more in the curricula.

3.6 Romania

3.6.1 Overview of the Education System

In Romania, primary education encompasses grades 0-IV, serving children aged 6-11. Secondary education is divided into lower secondary (grades 5-8, ages 11-14) and upper secondary (grades 9-12, ages 15-18). The Romanian national curriculum integrates sustainability concepts transversally across subjects, focusing on topics like environmental protection, social equity, active participation, and responsible consumption. The National Strategy on Education for the Environment and Climate Change (2023–2030) promotes a systemic approach to education for sustainable development, emphasizing the balance between human needs and planetary limits, intergenerational justice, and both personal and collective involvement.

3.6.2 Definitions

In the Romanian national curriculum, the terms "sustainability," "sustainable development," and "competence for sustainability" are not explicitly defined in the key documents of primary and secondary education. However, the concepts associated with sustainability are integrated across the curriculum, particularly through topics such as environmental protection, social equity, active participation and responsible consumption. For example, the National Strategy on Education for the Environment and Climate Change (2023–2030) promotes a systemic approach to education for sustainable development, focused on the balance between human needs and the planet's limits, while emphasizing the role of intergenerational justice and personal and collective involvement (GD 1176/2022).

It's important to note that the term "sustainability" (*sustenabilitate*) does not formally appear in existing framework plans or curricula. The current framework plans, developed since 2016, and previous programs, such as the one for the Natural Sciences discipline in grades III and IV (2014), focus on skills training, but without a clear definition or set of objectives dedicated to sustainability. The construction of these programs aims to align with European frameworks such as TIMSS and the European Parliament's Recommendation on Key Competences for Lifelong Learning (2006/962/EC). Although these documents indirectly contribute to the development of sustainability-relevant competences – such as scientific,

social, civic thinking and initiative – they do not include an integrated and coherent approach, as proposed in GreenComp, which provides clear and structured definitions for sustainability, sustainable development and associated competences.

3.6.3 Four Dimensions of Sustainability

The national curriculum in Romania integrates the concepts of social, cultural and economic sustainability in a transversal way, even if it does not always formulate them explicitly.

- **Environmental Sustainability:** Integrated through topics such as environmental protection, present across the curriculum and emphasized in initiatives like the "Eco-School" program and "Green Week".
- **Social Sustainability:** Emphasized in subjects like Civic Education, Social Education, and Counselling and Personal Development, focusing on values and skills such as equity, democratic participation, tolerance, and social responsibility.
- **Cultural Sustainability:** Promoted through the development of values such as respect for cultural diversity, also addressed in subjects like History and Social Education.
- **Economic Sustainability:** Directly addressed in Entrepreneurial Education and Economic Education programs, covering concepts like limited resources, financial planning, and circular economy.

Inclusion and social sustainability are particularly emphasized from the primary cycle through Counseling and Orientation classes, focusing on socio-emotional skills, empathy, cooperation and peaceful conflict resolution, and further deepened in higher cycles. Extracurricular initiatives like "Project Week," "Green Week," the "Eco-School" program, and school-community partnerships contribute to pro-social and responsible attitudes, providing real-world contexts for applying sustainability values.

3.6.4 GreenComp Competence Areas in Romanian School Curricula

The Romanian curricular documents address the four competence areas of GreenComp, although not always explicitly using the GreenComp terminology.

Embodying Sustainability Values: The national curriculum supports the formation of values and attitudes related to sustainability mainly through disciplines such as "Counseling and Personal Development," "Social Education," and "Counseling and Guidance," present from secondary school to high school. These subjects promote self-knowledge, empathy, effective communication, cooperation and personal responsibility, which are essential skills for social

sustainability. Students are encouraged to reflect on their own values and behaviors through active methods such as self-assessments, debates, thematic projects and service-learning initiatives, developing a social conscience and motivating them to adopt a lifestyle based on responsibility, solidarity and mutual respect. At the high school level, guidance and counselling subjects integrate topics such as career ethics, gender equity, cultural diversity and civic engagement, contributing to a sustainable and inclusive vision of the future. Even if the term sustainability is not frequently mentioned explicitly, the fundamental values associated with it are deeply rooted in educational objectives and current school practice.

Embracing Complexity: The Romanian curriculum encourages systems thinking and understanding of interdependencies especially through disciplines such as Counseling and Personal Development, Social Education, Geography and Biology, but also through interdisciplinary approaches that link social, economic and ecological aspects. Students learn to identify cause-and-effect relationships, connect global and local issues, and recognize the impact of their own actions on broader systems, developing essential skills for systems thinking and understanding sustainability challenges. The curriculum also promotes critical thinking and decision-making in uncertain contexts through reflective and exploratory activities that stimulate debate, comparative analysis, and consideration of multiple perspectives. Students are exposed to topics such as climate change, social inequalities, migration, or excessive consumption, either through curricular content or extracurricular activities (e.g., "Project Week" or Erasmus projects). Even though terms such as 'complex problems' or 'hard-to-manage global problems' are not formally used in curriculum documents, students are supported to engage in learning through interdisciplinary collaboration, thematic projects and solution-centric approaches, thus developing a deeper understanding of the complexity of the contemporary world.

Envisioning Sustainable Futures: The national curriculum in Romania supports students to imagine and shape sustainable futures through various disciplines and educational contexts, such as Counseling and Personal Development, Civic Education and Social Education, and extracurricular activities. Especially in middle school and high school, students are guided to reflect on their personal values, interests and resources, to formulate future goals and to develop educational and professional plans. This approach encourages long-term thinking, autonomy in decision-making and awareness of the personal impact on society. Skills such as imagination, creativity, literacy in future scenarios, adaptability and innovation are developed through interactive activities: projects, debates, scenarios, role-playing and learning based on real problems. Students are encouraged to create alternative solutions to the challenges of modern society – from environmental protection and social inclusion to reducing inequalities and using resources responsibly. Initiatives such as "Project Week", collaborations with NGOs and participation in thematic clubs help them to practice their

ability to think creatively and act positively. These practices promote a solution-oriented and change-oriented mindset that is necessary in building a fair, sustainable, and resilient future.

Acting for Sustainability: The national curriculum in Romania encourages the involvement of students in individual and collective actions for a sustainable future through curricular and extracurricular activities, with a focus on civic responsibility, personal initiative and environmental awareness. Subjects such as Counseling and Personal Development, Civic Education and Social Education offer concrete contexts in which students identify real problems in their lives or in the community and propose applied solutions, through group activities, awareness campaigns or volunteering projects. National programmes such as "Project Week" and initiatives carried out in partnership with NGOs (e.g. Eco-School, Let's Do It Romania) strengthens collective action, teamwork and students' motivation to get actively involved in the social and environmental issues around them. Although the terms 'competence to act', 'agency' or 'initiative' are not explicitly used in official curriculum documents, they are reflected in the cross-cutting objectives aimed at forming critical thinking, personal responsibility and democratic participation. In the Civic Education curriculum (eighth grade), students are familiarized with democratic structures, citizens' rights and obligations, and forms of civic participation through peaceful methods, such as petitions, public campaigns, expressing opinions, or getting involved in community initiatives. Also, the National Strategy on Education for Environment and Climate Change (Ministerul Educației, România, 2022) proposes the development of a culture of responsibility towards the environment and society, in which students are supported to make informed decisions and act as agents of change. Thus, by combining the formal curriculum with educational policy initiatives, the education system in Romania contributes to the formation of young people capable of building sustainable, equitable and resilient societies.

3.6.5 Teacher Education and Leadership Training

In Romania, initial teacher training includes general competencies related to critical thinking, civic education, social equity and personal development, but education for sustainability is not systematically or explicitly addressed in the framework plans of initial training programs, such as the Psycho Pedagogical Module or the Didactic Master's Degree. Although some universities introduce ecological or interdisciplinary content within pedagogical disciplines, they depend on the initiative of university teachers or institutional projects. Promisingly, the National Strategy on Education for the Environment and Climate Change (2023–2030) proposes that all initial teacher training programmes include an environmental and climate education component, alongside the development of a culture of sustainability in schools (edu.ro). According to national research and reports, teachers' confidence in teaching for sustainability is medium to low, especially in the absence of specialized training and clearly

defined curricular resources. For example, the Education and Training Monitor 2023 – Romania report highlights that, although Romanian teachers recognize the importance of education for the environment and sustainability, many do not feel sufficiently prepared to integrate these topics transversally and effectively into teaching (op.europa.eu). Continuing professional development programmes, such as courses offered by CCDs or platforms such as CRED, include in some cases modules on education for active citizenship, environment and sustainable lifestyle, but these are not yet compulsory or systematised at national level. The need for an integrated, coherent and mandatory approach in preparing teachers and school leaders for sustainability remains a key challenge.

3.6.6 Identified Good Practices

The curricular and other education policy/research documents of Romania encourage several good practices in sustainability education:

- **Optional Subjects:** Schools and teachers have the autonomy to elaborate and propose optional subjects for the students, chosen from a list of the Ministry of Education or projected as a new subject, offering an opportunity to introduce sustainability topics.
- **Social and Emotional Competences:** Integration of good practices for teachers to develop students' social and emotional skills, supporting social sustainability.
- **"Project Week" and "Green Week" Program:** The introduction of two annual weeks dedicated to non-formal learning provides space for interdisciplinary thematic projects, including activities related to environmental protection, volunteering and community involvement. Teachers have autonomy in planning, and students are encouraged to actively participate.
- **Eco-School:** A program recognized by the Ministry of Education, present in many schools, promoting environmental education, student involvement in environmental protection, recycling and consumption reduction. The activities are coordinated in student-teacher-community teams, supporting collaboration and civic responsibility.
- **CRED Project:** A national initiative that provided guides, teaching resources and continuous training for teachers, encouraging active learning methods, the integration of transversal competences and the development of critical thinking. It advocates the inclusion of education for sustainability and harnessing teacher autonomy in lesson design.

- **"Let's Do It, Romania!"** and **"Earth Hour"** programs in schools: Initiatives promoted through partnerships between NGOs and school inspectorates, involving students in cleaning, planting, recycling, and education actions for green energy, encouraging collective action, social responsibility and school-community collaboration.
- **Education for sustainable development in the extended curriculum:** Sustainable development is integrated transversally into the national curriculum through themes such as responsible consumption, human rights, social equity, and healthy lifestyle. They are approached flexibly, offering teaching autonomy and openness to topical issues, such as climate change or social inequalities.

3.6.7 Assessment of Sustainability Competences

The national curriculum in Romania promotes a competency-centric approach, including the assessment of sustainability-related dimensions through varied and flexible methods. According to the National Curriculum Reference Framework (Institute of Education Sciences, 2017), it is recommended to use practices such as self-assessment, portfolios, applied projects, peer assessment, reflective journals and practical demonstration of competences in real contexts. These methods allow not only the measurement of knowledge, but also the level of involvement, responsibility, critical thinking and proactive attitude of students in relation to environmental and social challenges. They are applied especially in disciplines such as Civic Education, Counseling and Personal Development or in extracurricular activities with sustainability themes.

Regarding teacher training, the National Strategy on Education for the Environment and Climate Change (2023–2030) highlights the need to include in teachers' training assessment skills relevant to the field of sustainability, as well as the development of specific tools. Although there is still no standardised assessment framework for these competences, initiatives such as the '4E-Education' project (4E-Education, 2024) aim to digitalise assessment and create a national platform that includes items and resources for sustainability assessment. In the absence of dedicated local tools, organizations such as Teach for Romania (Țolescu, 2025) use international solutions (e.g. Panorama Education) to assess socio-emotional skills, which are essential for sustainability. These examples point to real progress, but also underline the need for a coherent national skills assessment strategy for a sustainable future.

3.6.8 Key Strengths and Gaps

The Romanian curriculum integrates sustainability concepts across various subjects, promoting interdisciplinary approaches. There is a focus on developing social and emotional

skills alongside environmental awareness. Extracurricular activities and programs like "Project Week" and "Eco-School" provide practical contexts for sustainability education. Teacher autonomy is supported in designing optional subjects and incorporating sustainability themes.

However, like in many other countries' curricula, sustainability terms are not always explicitly defined in core curriculum documents and initial teacher training does not systematically address sustainability education. In addition, there is a need for more standardized assessment tools and frameworks for sustainability competences. Practical, experiential learning, especially in natural settings, could be further emphasized.

3.7 Spain

3.7.1 Overview of the Education System

In Spain, primary education is structured into 6 grades (EP 1 to 6), catering to children aged 6 to 12 years old. Secondary education is divided into lower secondary education, comprising 4 grades (ESO 1 to 4), for students aged 12 to 16 years. The Spanish national curriculum, particularly the LOMLOE (Ley Orgánica 3/2020), integrates sustainability into education through cross-cutting approaches embedded in educational objectives, values, and content. The curriculum emphasizes the knowledge, skills, values, and attitudes necessary for a full life and responsible global citizenship, incorporating sustainable development into all compulsory education programs (primary and secondary education).

3.7.2 Definitions

The LOMLOE (2020) and GreenComp (2022) both integrate sustainability into education, but with slightly different approaches. In Spain, the concepts of "sustainability" and "sustainable competence" are mainly integrated through cross-cutting approaches incorporated into educational objectives, values, and content. The LOMLOE establishes that sustainable development should be part of all compulsory education programs (primary and secondary education), emphasizing the knowledge, skills, values and attitudes necessary for a full life and responsible global citizenship (LOMLOE, Preamble, p. 6; Sixth Additional Provision, p. 73; and Article 1, which amends Article 2 of the LOE). While the law doesn't explicitly define "sustainability competence," it adopts a competency-based educational model and refers to the acquisition of key competencies as essential learning outcomes.

3.7.3 Four Dimensions of Sustainability

The Spanish national curriculum (LOMLOE, 2020) explicitly addresses social, cultural, and economic sustainability alongside environmental sustainability. This is achieved through a transversal educational approach that integrates these dimensions into all stages of

compulsory education, with specific subject areas and pedagogical principles aligned to them.

- **Environmental Sustainability:** Integrated across the curriculum and emphasized in subjects like Natural Sciences and Geography.
- **Social Sustainability:** Emphasized through "Educación en Valores Cívicos y Éticos" (Education in Civic and Ethical Values) and pedagogical principles promoting equality, inclusion, and social justice.
- **Cultural Sustainability:** Addressed within the broader context of social sustainability, promoting respect for diversity and cultural awareness.
- **Economic Sustainability:** Covered in "Educación en Valores Cívicos y Éticos" and related subjects, including topics like the role of taxes and responsible consumption.

In primary education, these elements are introduced in the subject area Educación en Valores Cívicos y Éticos, particularly in the third cycle, where students are taught about the role of taxes, justice, human rights, sustainability, and diversity. In secondary education, similar content appears in the same subject (Educación en Valores Cívicos y Éticos), where ethical reflection, democratic values, social equity, and environmental awareness are central. Inclusion and social sustainability are emphasized most explicitly in the pedagogical principles of both primary and secondary education. In primary education, inclusion is addressed through personalized attention, early support for learning difficulties, and promotion of values such as equality and social justice. In secondary education, inclusion appears in the educational objectives, teaching methods, and curricular adaptations for diverse learners, including students with special needs.

3.7.4 GreenComp Competence Areas in Spanish School Curricula

Embodying Sustainability Values: The LOMLOE promotes an ethical and inclusive approach to sustainability by integrating social, cultural and environmental dimensions in all compulsory education stages. It promotes social sustainability by emphasizing equality, inclusion and civic responsibility as fundamental educational principles. Subjects like Educación en Valores Cívicos y Éticos familiarize students with concepts such as human dignity, gender equality and environmental responsibility. This aligns with GreenComp's focus on fairness and shared responsibility and encourages learners to develop a critical and empathetic understanding of sustainability in social contexts. Students are motivated to reflect on their personal values and develop a sense of responsibility for sustainability in their daily lives through curriculum content and teaching strategies. The LOMLOE encourages active and participatory learning, including project work and community

engagement, incorporating sustainability into students' daily lives. Transversal themes invite students to reflect on the consequences of their actions and cultivate their civic awareness. This values-based education supports the development of a sustainable mindset and aligns with the GreenComp approach, which encourages ethical awareness and personal responsibility in real-world situations.

Embracing Complexity: The Spanish curriculum promotes cooperation between different subjects through an interdisciplinary organization that favors the combination of content from different areas. The school system allows for classifying subjects into broader fields of study, especially in primary and secondary education, enabling joint work on sustainability issues. This organization facilitates teacher collaboration and supports educational experiences that consider sustainability from various perspectives: scientific, ethical, social and economic. Cross-cutting skills, such as civic engagement, equity and environmental awareness, further strengthen collaboration in developing sustainability-related skills. The educational objectives of the LOMLOE include students' ability to analyze their environment, question beliefs and make informed choices, fostered through active and reflective learning approaches in all subjects. Although the legislation does not directly mention 'systems thinking', the competency-based orientation of the curriculum, combined with the integration of various disciplines, supports a comprehensive understanding of sustainability issues. Students are encouraged to recognize the interconnectedness between social, environmental and economic processes, aligning with the GreenComp principle of embracing complexity. The curriculum encourages students to face complicated global challenges by including real social and environmental issues in subjects like civics and ethics, social sciences, geography and history, as well as biology and geology. Global issues such as climate change, inequality in resource distribution, migration and declining biodiversity are addressed. Through critical discussions, case studies and community projects, students are invited to understand the causes and consequences of these 'difficult problems' and reflect on responsible behaviour.

Envisioning Sustainable Futures: Although not explicitly mentioned, the curriculum includes aspects related to GreenComp's aim to prepare students to anticipate, evaluate, and create positive futures. This is evident in the emphasis on fostering students' independence, creativity, and initiative—skills considered fundamental for navigating complex and unpredictable social and environmental changes. Subjects like Civic and Ethical Values Education, Social Sciences, Technology, Artistic Education, and Natural Sciences provide opportunities for students to explore possible responses to global challenges and share their visions of alternative futures through project-based and participatory learning. The LOMLOE supports active methodologies and interdisciplinary learning environments, encouraging students to generate innovative solutions to real-world problems.

Acting for Sustainability: The Spanish education system advocates for a holistic and formative approach to assessment, focused on measuring skills, including those related to sustainability. While there is no specific national tool dedicated exclusively to assessing sustainability competences, the LOMLOE encourages the use of formative and continuous assessment to measure students' development in transversal areas such as ethical awareness, social responsibility, and active citizenship. Article 25 (primary education) and Article 34 (secondary education) specify that assessment must consider students' progress in all competences, which implicitly includes sustainability-related dimensions. Furthermore, the subject *Educación en Valores Cívicos y Éticos*, which addresses social justice, environmental awareness, and civic engagement, is subject to regular evaluation and requires learners to demonstrate not only knowledge but also attitudes and practical engagement. This aligns with the GreenComp approach, which frames sustainability as a dynamic combination of knowledge, skills and attitudes. Regarding teacher education, Real Decreto 276/2007 focuses primarily on recruitment and access to teaching professions rather than defining competences explicitly. However, it includes evaluation of teaching aptitude and the design of didactic units during the opposition phase (Art. 21), which often require candidates to propose learning and assessment strategies for cross-curricular competences, including sustainability where relevant. While there is no explicit mandate for sustainability competence assessment, the teacher's capacity to apply inclusive, ethical, and competence-based assessment is essential and often expected in practice. Although national curriculum documents do not prescribe a standardized toolkit for sustainability assessment, Autonomous Communities and schools have the flexibility to adopt or develop their own evaluation instruments aligned with the national competence framework. These are increasingly informed by international guidelines such as GreenComp or UNESCO's ESD indicators, especially within innovative or experimental programs.

3.7.5 Teacher Education and Leadership Training

In Spain, there are ongoing efforts to integrate sustainability competences into education systems, focusing on equipping teachers and school leaders with the necessary skills. This involves embedding sustainability in teacher competence frameworks, initial teacher education, and professional development programs, achieved through courses and training offered by the education department. Programs aimed at transforming schools into green schools and specific sustainability initiatives contribute to this process. While awareness and concern for sustainability are generally high among in-service teachers, access to and dissemination of professional development training programs can be improved to further enhance their preparedness.

3.7.6 Identified Good Practices

Spain's curricular and related education policy/research documents encourage these good practices in sustainability education:

- The new VET level law incorporates a specific subject focused on sustainability.
- The green schools network is implemented in many schools nationally, with each green association designing a yearly local project.
- The promotion of green and sustainable mobility for schools encourages centers to adopt these practices, with associated awards and recognition.
- Local city halls establish student association groups or councils to involve students in assessing the environmental situation and designing/implementing local sustainability initiatives.

3.7.7 Assessment of Sustainability Competences

The Spanish education system, through the LOMLOE, employs a holistic and formative assessment approach measuring skills, including sustainability-related ones. While no specific national tool exists for sustainability competence assessment, the law mandates evaluating progress in all competences, implicitly including sustainability, as seen in Civic and Ethical Values Education. Teacher training (Real Decreto 276/2007) focuses on recruitment but evaluates teaching abilities, where candidates often suggest sustainability-related assessment strategies. Although no direct sustainability assessment requirement exists for teachers, inclusive and competence-based assessment is expected. National guidelines lack fixed assessment tools, allowing Autonomous Communities and schools to adopt or create their own, increasingly influenced by international standards like GreenComp and UNESCO's ESD indicators in innovative projects.

3.7.8 Key Strengths and Gaps

The Spanish curriculum effectively integrates sustainability across environmental, social, cultural, and economic dimensions. Legal frameworks such as LOMLOE and various policy documents underscore the significance of sustainability education. Numerous commendable practices exist at both national and local levels, exemplified by green school networks and student environmental councils. Furthermore, the curriculum actively encourages learning, civic engagement, and critical thinking specifically related to sustainability.

Despite these strengths, there are areas for improvement. While sustainability is incorporated into the curriculum, its practical application within teacher training could be

enhanced. The assessment of sustainability competences could benefit from becoming more explicit and standardized across the education system. Additionally, the curriculum could be further strengthened by providing a wider array of tools and innovative ideas to support schools in effectively addressing complex sustainability issues. Finally, there is an identified need to increase the amount of time students spend learning in natural environments to deepen their understanding and connection to sustainability principles.

3.8 Türkiye

3.8.1 Overview of the Education System

In Türkiye, primary education spans grades 1–4, catering to children aged 6–9. Secondary education is divided into lower secondary (grades 5–8, ages 10–13) and upper secondary (grades 9–12, ages 14–17) levels. The national curriculum, known as the Türkiye Yüzyılı Maarif Modeli (Education Model for the Turkish Century), promotes a holistic development encompassing moral, intellectual, physical, and emotional growth. It emphasizes ecological awareness, social responsibility, and the cultivation of national and humanitarian values.

3.8.2 Definitions

In the Türkiye Yüzyılı Maarif Modeli (Education Model for the Turkish Century) (2024), the concept of sustainability is not defined explicitly using the exact term as used in GreenComp. However, it is deeply embedded in the educational philosophy that promotes a 'competent and virtuous individual'. The curriculum highlights the importance of holistic development, encompassing moral, intellectual, physical, and emotional growth. It underscores ecological awareness, social responsibility, and the cultivation of national and humanitarian values. This perspective aligns with GreenComp's (Bianchi, Pisiotis & Cabrera Giraldez, 2022) definition of sustainability, which involves prioritizing planetary and societal well-being. GreenComp frames sustainability competence as the ability to take or advocate for action to support ecosystem health and justice. The Türkiye curriculum echoes these principles through its Virtue-Value-Action framework, which integrates environmental sensitivity, ethical responsibility, and cultural rootedness into educational goals. Although Turkish does not have a direct translation for 'sustainability competence', terms such as responsibility, sensitivity, and virtue are used to represent overlapping meanings.

3.8.3 Four Dimensions of Sustainability

The Türkiye Yüzyılı Maarif Modeli (Education Model for the Turkish Century) explicitly and implicitly addresses all four dimensions of sustainability: environmental, social, cultural, and economic.

- **Environmental Sustainability:** Addressed through themes such as environmental responsibility, health, cleanliness, and nature sensitivity within the student profile and curriculum goals.
- **Social Sustainability:** Deeply interwoven through values like justice, cooperation, empathy, and civic responsibility.
- **Cultural Sustainability:** Highly emphasized, particularly through the curriculum's strong focus on national values, cultural heritage, and language education. The program advocates for cultural continuity and awareness, supporting identity development and intergenerational transmission of values.
- **Economic Sustainability:** More implicit but observable in references to responsibility, productivity, and alignment with life skills and vocational preparedness in upper secondary programs.

Inclusivity and equity are critical, especially in supporting disadvantaged groups, ensuring education as a right, and planning equitable learning experiences.

3.8.4 GreenComp Competence Areas

The Türkiye Yüzyılı Maarif Modeli (Education Model for the Turkish Century) addresses the four competence areas defined by GreenComp, although it frames them within its own educational philosophy and objectives.

Embodying Sustainability Values: The curriculum strongly fosters sustainability values through its Virtue-Value-Action framework. Students are guided to reflect on concepts such as justice, empathy, compassion, and environmental awareness. Moral and ethical development is an explicit aim of education, integrating values education in all subjects. The holistic student profile model envisions learners as responsible citizens who care for themselves, their communities, and nature. This approach mirrors GreenComp's emphasis on embodying sustainability values, especially in fostering empathy, care, and ethical decision-making. Social sustainability is promoted by enabling students to understand the importance of fairness, dignity, and interdependence. Learning outcomes are designed to shape learners who internalize these values and act accordingly in personal and public life.

Embracing Complexity: Türkiye Yüzyılı Maarif Modeli (Education Model for the Turkish Century) encourages interdisciplinary learning and systems thinking, core elements in addressing sustainability complexity. It proposes a curriculum structure that promotes cross-cutting themes and transdisciplinary approaches. Systemic understanding is encouraged via the Systems Thinking framework and project-based, inquiry-driven learning experiences. Students are taught to analyze problems from multiple perspectives, connecting scientific, cultural, and social disciplines. Critical and analytical thinking are explicitly mentioned as expected outcomes. This aligns well with GreenComp's dimension of

complexity and systems thinking, promoting learners' ability to navigate uncertainty and interconnected challenges.

Envisioning Sustainable Futures: The curriculum encourages students to envision alternative futures through structured learning environments that emphasize creativity, imagination, and critical thinking. Disciplinary and interdisciplinary learning experiences—such as project-based and inquiry-based learning—promote the development of future literacy. Students are guided to imagine a more equitable, sustainable, and inclusive society by reflecting on ethical values, societal issues, and cultural heritage. Türkiye Yüzyılı Maarif Modeli (Education Model for the Turkish Century) also promotes adaptability and personal goal setting as core learner traits. Through social-emotional learning and student-centered activities, students are equipped to respond to complex realities and imagine new possibilities. This vision aligns with GreenComp's emphasis on future-oriented skills, such as adaptability and innovation.

Acting for Sustainability: Learners are encouraged to take both individual and collective action through social responsibility projects, civic engagement, and environmental practices in the school context. The program supports participatory experiences where students engage with their community and propose solutions to real-world challenges. This includes school-based planning and decision-making opportunities that reinforce action competence. Although the term 'agency' is not directly used, the curriculum promotes initiative-taking, leadership, and ethical responsibility. This mirrors GreenComp's call for learners to become agents of change and to act for sustainability in systemic and impactful ways. Programs such as Lifelong Learning and Social Responsibility integrate lifelong engagement and practical activism into the educational model.

3.8.5 Teacher Education and Leadership Training

In Türkiye, teacher and school leader training includes both pre-service university programs and in-service professional development under the Ministry of National Education. Pre-service curricula developed by YÖK include environmental science, moral education, and community engagement, but sustainability is not yet addressed as an interdisciplinary or holistic theme. Teacher candidates may acquire partial competencies through elective courses or classroom management practices with sustainability-related values. In-service training offered by MEB includes summer schools, webinars, and school-based professional development activities. A significant step toward institutionalizing teacher training came in 2025, with the launch of the 'Öğretmen Akademisi' (Teacher Academy). This national initiative aims to establish a systematic and high-quality framework for professional learning, offering structured training modules in areas including digital transformation, inclusive education, and sustainability. The Teacher Academy emphasizes alignment with international competence frameworks such as GreenComp, ensuring that in-service training

supports teachers in developing the full range of sustainability competencies. Modules are designed to be interdisciplinary and practice-oriented, supporting school leaders and educators in applying sustainability concepts across subject areas and daily practice. In-service training by MEB includes summer schools, webinars, and school-based professional development that occasionally address sustainability, digitalization, or inclusive education. However, there is no systematic national framework for building teachers' or leaders' full sustainability competences. Professional development needs to be further aligned with the four GreenComp competence areas to ensure deep, actionable integration in practice.

3.8.6 Good Practices

- **Ekokul Program** – A national implementation of the international Eco-Schools program promoting student-led environmental action and whole-school engagement.
- **Sıfır Atık Eğitimleri** – Government-led waste-reduction training and school-based initiatives encouraging sustainable consumption and waste management.
- **Sosyal Sorumluluk Projeleri** – Student projects in many secondary schools address themes of inclusion, cultural heritage, and environmental care through community service.
- **Okul Tabanlı Gelişim (OTG) Planları** – These plans allow schools to develop context-based programs that include sustainability and wellbeing practices.
- **Hayat Boyu Öğrenme Etkinlikleri** – Lifelong learning activities in public education centers support intergenerational education on sustainable living.

3.8.7 Assessment of Sustainability Competences

The Turkish curriculum promotes process-based and multidimensional assessment methods that reflect student growth in values, attitudes, and actions. Assessment strategies include performance tasks, learning evidence collections, and teacher reflections. These methods allow for the evaluation of students' sustainability-related attitudes and behaviours.

Although there is no national tool specifically named for sustainability competence assessment, the emphasis on observing ethical behavior, social engagement, and environmental actions implies embedded evaluation. Teacher education and professional development programs also include reflective practice components to strengthen assessment literacy.

3.8.8 Key Strengths and Gaps

The Turkish curriculum demonstrates strengths in integrating sustainability-related values and goals across various subjects. It emphasizes a holistic approach to development, encompassing moral, social, and ecological awareness among students. Furthermore,

several good practices are present, such as the widespread Eco-Schools program and various Social Responsibility Projects undertaken by students. The initiation of the Teacher Academy also signifies a positive step towards a more systematized approach to teacher training in the area of sustainability.

Notwithstanding, certain gaps exist within the Turkish education system regarding sustainability. There is currently no unified framework specifically dedicated to sustainability education, which could lead to inconsistencies in implementation. The training of teachers and school leaders needs a stronger and more explicit integration of the GreenComp competences to ensure educators are well-equipped. Finally, a more coherent cross-curricular policy for sustainability is necessary to weave these principles effectively throughout the entire educational experience.

4. Cross-Country comparative analysis/synthesis

4.1 Commonalities across countries

Across the eight countries examined, a notable commonality is the integration of environmental sustainability into their national curricula. Each nation emphasizes environmental protection, ecological awareness, and the importance of preserving natural resources for future generations. This often translates into specific subjects like Natural Sciences, Geography, and Environmental Education, as well as participation in initiatives like the Eco-Schools program. The commitment to addressing climate change and promoting responsible consumption habits is also consistently present, demonstrating a shared global understanding of the urgency and importance of environmental issues.

Another recurring theme is the emphasis on social sustainability, particularly the promotion of equity, inclusion, and social justice. Countries highlight the importance of developing students' civic responsibility, ethical awareness, and empathy. Civic Education and Social Education courses often focus on democratic participation, human rights, tolerance, and cooperation. Additionally, there is a shared effort to address cultural sustainability by fostering respect for cultural diversity and promoting intercultural understanding, frequently through language, literature, and history subjects. These commonalities indicate a global recognition of the need to build societies that are both environmentally conscious and socially cohesive.

Furthermore, the integration of interdisciplinary approaches and project-based learning is evident across the countries. Many curricula advocate for connecting different subjects to tackle complex sustainability issues, encouraging students to see the interconnectedness of ecological, social, and economic dimensions. This approach aims to develop students' systems thinking, critical thinking, and problem-solving skills. Initiatives such as "Project Week" and student-led projects provide practical contexts for applying knowledge and engaging in real-world sustainability actions. The shared adoption of these pedagogical strategies reflects a global shift towards more holistic and action-oriented education, better preparing students to address the multifaceted challenges of sustainability.

Finally, while the approaches and definitions may vary, all countries strive to embed sustainability values within their education systems. There is a universal aspiration to foster responsible global citizens who are aware of their impact on the planet and society. Many nations aim to develop students' agency and encourage them to take initiative and act for sustainability, whether individually or collectively. This commitment is visible in the support for student participation in decision-making, community engagement, and advocacy. Ultimately, the shared goal is to equip students with the knowledge, skills, and values needed to create a more sustainable and just future, despite the unique national contexts and priorities that also shape their educational systems.

4.2 Differences and country-specific challenges

This section outlines the key differences and specific challenges identified in the integration of sustainability education across the various countries analyzed: Bulgaria, Finland, Greece, Hungary, Portugal, Romania, and Spain.

Bulgaria

Bulgaria's curriculum integrates sustainability principles across subjects but often implicitly rather than explicitly. A significant challenge is the transition from implicit to explicit teaching of "competence for sustainability." Teacher training varies in confidence and readiness to address sustainability issues. There's also a need for more practical, hands-on learning experiences, especially in underserved areas. While the curriculum aims for interdisciplinary approaches, consistent implementation and monitoring are gaps.

Finland

Finland is known for its strong emphasis on student well-being and equity, and its curriculum defines sustainability through "ecosocial knowledge and ability." A primary challenge in Finland lies in translating high knowledge levels into collective action. Research indicates that action competence often results in individual behavior change but not always collective action. The upper secondary curriculum mentions sustainability less frequently than basic education. Although diverse assessment methods are used, a national tool for explicitly assessing sustainability competencies is lacking, leading to varied implementation.

Greece

Greece integrates sustainability through interdisciplinary and project-based learning, aligning with the EU's GreenComp framework. A challenge in Greece is the tension between exam-centered curricula and experiential learning. Despite policy efforts, integrating sustainability into daily school life and structures remains difficult. There's a concern that formal education could overshadow non-formal, informal, and nature-based learning. In-service teachers have moderate awareness but limited confidence in comprehensively addressing sustainability challenges.

Hungary

Hungary's curriculum defines "sustainability" as the harmonious interconnectedness of environmental, social, and economic aspects. A challenge is the need for more practical training and professional development opportunities for educators. Sustainability concepts are not always fully operationalized in teacher training, resulting in a lack of concrete tools and strategies for teachers. There's also an absence of standardized national assessment frameworks for sustainability competencies. While good practices like the Eco-school and Forest School programs exist, broader implementation and support are needed.

Portugal

Portugal integrates sustainability across different dimensions, with a strong emphasis on environmental education through initiatives like the Eco-Schools program. A significant gap is the lack of explicit tools and metrics for assessing sustainability competencies. Systems thinking and interdisciplinary collaboration, while encouraged, are not always structurally integrated. Competences around future literacy could be further emphasized. While teacher training is increasingly focused on sustainability, assessment methods for students remain undefined.

Romania

Romania integrates sustainability transversally across subjects, focusing on social and emotional skills alongside environmental awareness. A key challenge is that sustainability terms are not always explicitly defined in core curriculum documents. Initial teacher training does not systematically address sustainability education, and there's a need for more standardized assessment tools for sustainability competencies. Practical, experiential learning, especially in natural settings, could be further emphasized to strengthen the impact.

Spain

Spain's curriculum integrates sustainability through cross-cutting approaches. A primary challenge is ensuring consistent implementation of the competency-based model, especially in assessing key competencies related to sustainability. Teacher training and support in adapting to this model may vary. While there's emphasis on "Educación en Valores Cívicos y Éticos," translating this into practical, ongoing actions in schools can be difficult. The balance between formal education standards and integrating sustainability practices also presents an ongoing challenge.

Türkiye

Türkiye's curriculum integrates sustainability through a holistic model focusing on moral, intellectual, physical, and emotional growth, implicitly addressing environmental and social responsibility. A key challenge is the lack of an explicitly defined "sustainability competence" and a unified framework for sustainability education. Teacher training programs require stronger integration of GreenComp competences to build instructional capacity. While there are good practices such as the Eco-Schools program, a more coherent, cross-curricular policy is needed to ensure consistent integration of sustainability throughout the educational experience.

Comparative Analysis and Overarching Challenges

Comparing the countries, several overarching challenges emerge. Teacher training and support are consistently areas needing improvement. Many countries report that while teachers may understand the importance of sustainability, they lack the confidence or concrete tools to implement it effectively. This suggests a need for more robust, ongoing professional development.

Assessment of sustainability competencies is another common gap. Most countries rely on broader assessment methods related to civic participation, critical thinking, and problem-solving. However, specific frameworks or tools designed to measure sustainability competencies are often lacking. This makes it difficult to track progress and ensure accountability.

Furthermore, balancing formal education requirements with experiential, hands-on learning for sustainability is a widespread challenge. Many curricula aim for interdisciplinary and project-based learning, but the practical implementation can be hindered by exam-focused systems and time constraints. Engaging students in real-world activities and nature-based learning is essential but requires resources, planning, and systemic support.

Finally, the level of explicit definition and integration of sustainability concepts varies significantly. Some countries, like Finland, have clear definitions and frameworks (e.g., "ecosocial knowledge and ability"), while others integrate sustainability more implicitly. This disparity can lead to inconsistencies in teaching and learning outcomes.

While all the analyzed countries have made efforts to integrate sustainability education, each faces unique and common challenges. Addressing these challenges through improved teacher training, robust assessment frameworks, and a greater emphasis on experiential learning will be crucial in advancing education for sustainability. Each country can also learn from the successes and challenges of the others, fostering a collaborative approach to improving sustainability education across the board.

4.3 Overall alignment with GreenComp

The GreenComp framework, established by the European Commission, provides a valuable reference point for evaluating how national curricula across different countries address sustainability education. While there is a general trend toward integrating sustainability into educational policies and curricula, the degree and nature of alignment with GreenComp vary.

4.3.1 General Trends

Several common trends emerge from the analysis of the different countries' curricula:

- **Integration of Sustainability Concepts:** Most countries recognize the importance of incorporating sustainability into education. This is often done through cross-curricular approaches, integrating sustainability into various subjects.
- **Emphasis on Environmental Sustainability:** Environmental sustainability tends to be the most prominent dimension addressed in curricula, with a focus on topics like climate change, biodiversity, and resource conservation.
- **Growing Attention to Social Sustainability:** There's an increasing recognition of the importance of social sustainability, with curricula addressing themes of equity, inclusion, and social justice.
- **Varied Definitions of Sustainability:** While most countries incorporate the core ideas of sustainability, the specific definitions and terminology used can vary. Some curricula lack explicit definitions of "sustainability competence," while others integrate it implicitly.

4.3.2 Definitions of sustainability and related terms

Table 1 compares how the terms “sustainability”, “sustainable development”, and “sustainable competence” are defined in the country curricula as compared to the definitions in the GreenComp framework:

Concepts	Bulgarian curriculum	Finnish Curriculum	Greek Curriculum	Hungarian Curriculum	Portuguese Curriculum	Romanian Curriculum	Spanish Curriculum (LOMLOE)	Turkish Curriculum	GreenComp Framework
Sustainability	Implicit in the philosophy promoting balanced development, ecological awareness, and social responsibility in Ordinance no. 13.	Primarily defined through the concept of ecosocial knowledge and ability, emphasizing climate change awareness and responsible lifestyles, encompassing ecological, economic, social, and	Framed as an interdisciplinary, value-based concept rooted in environmental, social, cultural, and economic dimensions. Emphasizes environmental responsibility and developing skills to manage resources	Harmonious interconnectedness of environmental, social, and economic aspects to ensure balance for current and future generations.	Preservation of the environment for future generations	Not explicitly defined, but concepts are integrated transversally (e.g., environmental protection, social equity).	Integrated through cross-cutting approaches in educational objectives, values and content.	Implicit in the philosophy promoting a 'competent and virtuous individual', holistic development, ecological awareness, and social responsibility.	Prioritizing the needs of all life forms and the planet by ensuring human activity does not exceed planetary boundaries.

		cultural dimensions							
Sustainable Development	Ordinance No. 13 defines "sustainable development" as a key principle reflecting balanced development for present and future generations, encompassing ecological, social, and economic aspects.	Highlighted as needing pupils to develop a sustainable way of life, taking into account ecological, economic, social, and cultural dimensions	Mentioned as rooted in environmental, social, cultural, and economic dimensions. The "Active Citizen Actions curriculum" is based on the 17 Sustainable Development Goals	A complex and dynamic process of social development that seeks balance between environmental soundness, equity, and the economy.	Development model meeting present needs without compromising the future	Concepts integrated through topics in the National Strategy on Education for the Environment and Climate Change (2023-2030), focused on balancing human needs and planetary limits.	Should be incorporated into all compulsory education programs (primary and secondary).	Addressed through the overall goals of the Education Model for the Turkish Century, focusing on holistic development and values.	The many processes and pathways used to stimulate development or achieve progress in sustainable ways.
Sustainability Competence	Not explicitly defined as a standalone concept in national standards but is implied through the set of	Curricula do not explicitly use the term 'sustainability competence,' but transversal competence area T7	Not always explicitly labeled as "sustainable competence," but the curriculum emphasizes	Implied through the curriculum's emphasis on skills to promote social inclusion and social justice, and the ability	Knowledge, skills, and attitudes for responsible and empathetic behavior	Indirectly addressed through skills training in areas like scientific, social, and civic thinking, but lacks an	Implied through a competency-based educational model and the acquisition of	Not directly translated; related concepts include responsibility, sensitivity, and virtue, emphasizing	Empowers learners to embody sustainability values and embrace complex systems in order to take or

	knowledge, skills, and attitudes students are expected to acquire to apply sustainable development principles.	("Participation , involvement and building a sustainable future") closely aligns with GreenComp's definition	developing key competencies like systems thinking, empathy, critical reflection , future thinking, and civic engagement	to address complex sustainability problems.	towards the planet	integrated and coherent approach.	key competencies	the ability to act responsibly and ethically.	request action that restores and maintains ecosystem health and enhances justice, generating visions for sustainable futures.
--	--	--	--	---	--------------------	-----------------------------------	------------------	---	---

Table 1: Mapping of key sustainability related definitions across countries' curricula with GreenComp definitions

4.3.3 Alignment with GreenComp Competence Areas

The alignment with the four competence areas of GreenComp (Embodying Sustainability Values, Embracing Complexity, Envisioning Sustainable Futures, and Acting for Sustainability) also demonstrates a range of approaches:

- **Embodying Sustainability Values:** Most curricula promote values such as environmental awareness, ethical responsibility, and social justice, which align with this area.
- **Embracing Complexity:** There's a growing emphasis on systems thinking, critical thinking, and interdisciplinary approaches to address complex sustainability issues, although the degree of integration varies.
- **Envisioning Sustainable Futures:** Curricula are increasingly encouraging students to imagine and create pathways towards sustainable futures, fostering skills like imagination, creativity, and futures literacy.
- **Acting for Sustainability:** Many curricula promote student agency and action competence, encouraging participation in sustainability-related projects and initiatives

4.3.3 Country-wise mapping of GreenComp competence Areas

GreenComp Competence Area	Finland	Greece	Bulgaria	Hungary	Portugal	Romania	Spain	Türkiye
Sustainability Values	Strong emphasis on values like responsibility, equity, and care for people and nature, integrated across subjects and school culture.	Curriculum fosters awareness, ethical responsibility, and inclusion, with strong ties to ESD principles and UN SDGs.	Values are promoted, but integration is less explicit; focus on environmental ethics, social responsibility, and respect.	Values are strongly embedded, emphasizing ethical responsibility, social equity, and reflection on personal choices.	Values are promoted through citizenship education, emphasizing ethical behavior, social justice, and personal responsibility.	Values are fostered through subjects like Civic Education, focusing on empathy, cooperation, and ethical behavior.	Values are integrated with a focus on ethical and inclusive approaches, promoting fairness, equality, and civic responsibility.	Values are a core component, with a strong emphasis on moral and ethical development through a Virtue-Value-Action framework.
Embracing Complexity	Strong promotion of interdisciplinary and systems thinking, with real-world problem-based approaches and critical analysis.	Interdisciplinary and project-based learning fosters systems and critical thinking, addressing interconnectedness of issues.	Interdisciplinary approach is present; systems and critical thinking are promoted to understand interconnectedness.	Interdisciplinarity, systems thinking, and critical thinking are explicitly promoted to address complex issues.	Interdisciplinary collaboration and systems thinking are present, but explicit promotion of systems thinking as a competence is limited.	Systems and critical thinking are encouraged through interdisciplinary approaches and real-world problem analysis.	Interdisciplinary approach and competency-based learning support systems and critical thinking for understanding complexity.	Interdisciplinary learning and systems thinking are encouraged to understand the interconnectedness of environmental, social, and cultural systems.

<p>Envisioning Sustainable Futures</p>	<p>Creativity and future-oriented thinking are promoted through project work and student-led initiatives.</p>	<p>Futures thinking is encouraged through project-based learning and future scenario analysis, though not always explicitly termed "futures literacy."</p>	<p>Imagination and creativity are fostered, but futures thinking may be less explicitly structured in the curriculum.</p>	<p>Imagination and exploration of sustainable scenarios are encouraged to develop innovative solutions.</p>	<p>Creativity and problem-solving are used to envision alternative futures, but explicit references to "futures literacy" are limited.</p>	<p>Imagination and creative problem-solving are promoted through various subjects and extracurricular activities.</p>	<p>Skills for anticipating and creating positive futures are included, fostering independence, creativity, and initiative.</p>	<p>Students are encouraged to envision alternative futures through creativity, imagination, and future-oriented projects.</p>
<p>Acting for Sustainability</p>	<p>Strong emphasis on student agency, action competence, and participation in eco-projects and community engagement.</p>	<p>Student agency and participation are promoted through projects and community engagement, fostering active citizenship.</p>	<p>Student agency and participation are encouraged through projects and initiatives, promoting individual and collective action.</p>	<p>Curriculum supports action-oriented competencies, encouraging students to take initiative and participate in sustainability actions.</p>	<p>Student agency is promoted through participatory projects, encouraging engagement in environmental protection and social justice.</p>	<p>Student involvement in individual and collective actions is encouraged through curricular and extracurricular activities.</p>	<p>Student agency is fostered through participatory learning and community engagement, promoting active citizenship and responsibility.</p>	<p>Learners are encouraged to take individual and collective action through community projects, civic engagement, and environmental practices.</p>

Table 2: Mapping the four competence areas of the GreenComp framework with countries' curricula

4.4 Areas of improvement

A simple search of the Erasmus+ Project Results Platform using filters such as "Green Skills," "Inclusion, Promoting Equality and Non-Discrimination," and "Environment and Climate Change" for KA210 and KA220 projects reveals a substantial number of initiatives, exceeding one thousand ongoing projects, with a similar number of completed projects in these thematic areas. In contrast, other keywords like "STEM education," "entrepreneurship," and "AI in education" yield fewer than 400 project results each. This disparity highlights the EU's strong commitment to advancing education for sustainable development across all levels of education. It also reflects the pressing needs and challenges the EU continues to address in fostering sustainability and inclusion through education.

According to the Education and Training Monitor 2024 Comparative Report, many young people today embrace sustainability values. 83.6% believe in changing personal habits to be more environmentally friendly. However, only 29.8% report acting on these values in daily life, suggesting a gap between knowledge and action, likely due to insufficient support or opportunities to apply what they learn. Schools are beginning to address this by adopting whole-school approaches to learning for sustainability, though curricular integration across the EU remains uneven.

Figure 5 illustrates how action lacks despite embodying sustainability values across European countries. The indicator for "embodying sustainability values" reflects the percentage of students who agree that it's important to change personal habits to be more environmentally conscious. Meanwhile, the "acting for sustainability" indicator represents the average proportion of students who frequently engage in sustainable behaviors, such as buying second-hand clothing, conserving water and electricity, avoiding plastic packaging, reusing and repairing items, and minimizing food waste. Countries are listed in order based on their overall score for the acting for sustainability indicator, from lowest to highest. While many of the partner countries in this project are not included in the dataset, the comparison remains insightful and underscores the importance of encouraging not just awareness but also meaningful, everyday action toward sustainability.

Figure 5: 8th grade students' sustainability values and action for sustainability

(Source: European Commission Joint Research Centre, calculations based on IEA ICCS 2022)

While most EU countries support basic sustainability education, deeper competences like futures literacy are important for transforming anxiety or passivity into resilience and proactive behavior are rarely emphasized. Teaching often centers on simple, low-impact actions like waste sorting (reported by 83.9% of school principals) rather than tackling complex sustainability challenges. Despite limited formal training, many teachers feel confident discussing sustainability, yet transformative, action-oriented teaching methods are still not widely practiced. As a result, just 42.1% of young people feel they've had meaningful learning experiences related to sustainability in school (European Commission. Directorate General for Education, Youth, Sport and Culture., 2024)

5. Readiness Assessment

This chapter examines the readiness of eight partner countries (Bulgaria, Finland, Greece, Hungary, Portugal, Romania, Spain, and Türkiye) to embed Education for Sustainable Development (ESD) and inclusion (source) within their national school curricula. The analysis focused on how national education systems translate these principles into practice, and to what extent they align with the European Sustainability Competence Framework (GreenComp) (Bianchi, Pisiotis, & Cabrera Giraldez, 2022).

To support this analysis, we undertook a multi-method data collection process. This included a systematic review of national core curriculum documents for basic and lower-secondary education (K–12), assessing how ESD and inclusion are defined, structured, and implemented at the policy level. Additionally, we conducted focus group interviews with school leaders, teachers, educators, and researchers who have direct experience in ESD, eco-social education, and inclusive teaching. These discussions provided country-specific insights into how policies are enacted in classrooms and where key gaps or innovations are emerging (Priestley, Biesta, & Robinson, 2015; van Poeck & Lysgaard, 2016).

To further understand the practical application of ESD and inclusive principles, we also collected and analysed examples of good practice from teachers and schools. This involved reviewing teacher blog posts, school websites, and existing national and international reports to identify pedagogical approaches that illustrate curriculum implementation in real-world contexts. These examples helped reveal how countries respond to the shared yet locally differentiated challenge of climate change—for instance, the contrast between Finland’s ecosystem-based approaches and Portugal’s focus on drought and desertification (UNESCO, 2020; Rieckmann, 2018).

Together, these data sources provided a comprehensive view of each country’s readiness which are defined here as the extent to which educational policies, curriculum content, teacher training, and school practices are in place and operationalised in ways that reflect the key competencies of the GreenComp framework and uphold principles of inclusion. Readiness also reflects the degree of coherence between policy and practice, and how well these systems address the needs of diverse learners in the context of sustainable development (Bianchi et al., 2022; European Agency for Special Needs and Inclusive Education [EASNIE], 2018).

To support comparative analysis, the findings are summarised in two visual tables: one for sustainability readiness, one for inclusion readiness. Each uses a symbolic and abbreviated system to convey the extent of implementation:

✓ = Fully implemented

◐ = Partially implemented

✘ = Not implemented

GCI-F / TT-P = Coded descriptors for GreenComp Integration (Full) / Teacher Training (Partial)

↑ / ↓ / → = Trend indicators (where applicable)

Criteria	Finland	Greece	Hungary	Portugal	Romania	Spain	Türkiye
Embodying sustainability values	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Embracing complexity in sustainability	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Envisioning sustainable futures	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	◦	◦
Acting for sustainability	✓	◦	✓	✓	✓	✓	◦
Integration of GreenComp competences in curricula	GCI-F	GCI-F	GCI-F	GCI-F	GCI-F	GCI-F	GCI-F
Teacher training in ESD	TT-P	TT-P	TT-P	TT-P	TT-P	TT-P	TT-P
Assessment of sustainability competences	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗

Table 3. Comparative Assessment of Sustainability Competence Readiness

5.1 Inclusion Readiness

Inclusive education is integral to achieving social sustainability, which encompasses the creation of equitable, cohesive, and resilient societies. Social sustainability involves ensuring that all individuals have access to opportunities and resources, fostering social cohesion, and promoting well-being across diverse populations (Missimer, Robèrt, & Broman, 2017). In the educational context, inclusion refers to the systematic efforts to accommodate and support the diverse needs of all learners, thereby contributing to the broader goals of social sustainability. The Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), particularly SDG 4, underscore the importance of inclusive and equitable quality education. SDG 4 aims to "ensure inclusive and equitable quality education and promote lifelong learning opportunities for all," highlighting the necessity of addressing disparities and fostering inclusive learning environments (UNESCO, 2020). Achieving this goal requires a comprehensive understanding of how educational systems are prepared to implement inclusive practices effectively.

Ambika and Sheeja Vayola (2023) argue that inclusive education fosters social cohesion, economic empowerment, and environmental awareness by ensuring equal access to learning for all, particularly for marginalized groups. Their study highlights the barriers faced in implementation—such as inadequate infrastructure, social stigma, and insufficient teacher training—but also identifies strategic solutions including curriculum reform, teacher capacity-building, and community engagement. Inclusive education, as framed in their analysis, is not only a human right but also a catalyst for building more equitable and resilient societies aligned with the Sustainable Development Goals (Ambika & Sheeja Vayola, 2023).

Similarly, Hajisoteriou and Sorkos (2023) propose a "blended paradigm" of Sustainable Intercultural and Inclusive Education (SIIE), arguing that inclusive and intercultural education—though historically treated as separate—share philosophical foundations rooted in social justice, participation, and equity. Their comparative analysis identifies conceptual overlaps and practical synergies between the two approaches and calls for a unified educational model that supports both intra-generational and intergenerational equity. They frame SIIE as a necessary evolution of educational policy and practice to meet the complexity of contemporary societies and to ensure the sustainability of democratic, inclusive values for future generations (Hajisoteriou & Sorkos, 2023).

Building upon literature review, existing reports and the our own review of curricula, teachers' voices and good practices, we aim to critically review and compare the readiness of eight partner countries (Bulgaria, Finland, Greece, Hungary, Portugal, Romania, Spain, and Türkiye) to implement inclusive education practices. Readiness, in this context, refers to the extent to which educational policies, curricula, teacher training programs, and school practices are aligned to support inclusion.

The following country specific commentary on inclusion readiness draws upon three key data sources:

- Literature review and existing research (check Section 2 on Methodology).
- Curriculum Documents: These provide insights into the formal policies and frameworks that guide educational practices. Analyzing curriculum documents helps determine the extent to which inclusive principles are embedded at the policy level.
- Preliminary findings from Focus Group Interviews: Engaging with educators, school leaders, and other stakeholders through focus groups offers a practical perspective on how inclusive policies are implemented in classrooms. These discussions reveal the challenges and successes experienced by practitioners, providing a nuanced understanding of readiness. However, only initial findings from the focus groups are available at the time of publication of this study. Detailed findings from the focus groups will be presented in the deliverable D2.2 of the InclusiveFuture project.
- Selected initial Examples of Good Practice: Documenting and analyzing successful inclusive practices from various schools and educators highlight effective strategies and innovations. These examples serve as models for implementing inclusive education and demonstrate the potential for scalability and adaptation in different contexts. Again, only selected examples of good practices are available at the time of publication of this study. Existing examples are based on previous projects and initial interaction with educators during focus groups. A systematic collection of good practices will be conducted and reported in the deliverable D2.3 of the InclusiveFuture project.

By triangulating data from these sources, the assessment offers a comprehensive overview of each country's preparedness to foster inclusive education. This approach aligns with the recommendations of the Global Education Monitoring Report, which emphasizes the need for inclusive education systems to address the diverse needs of learners and promote social inclusion (UNESCO, 2020).

5.2 Comparative Analysis of Inclusion

Bulgaria

During recent years Bulgaria has made efforts to align its educational system with the EU's goals for sustainable and inclusive society. In line with this, Bulgaria has conducted several policy reforms regarding sustainable and inclusive education. One of the most important reforms is Ordinance 13 for civic, health, ecological and intercultural education. This document represents a step toward embedding sustainability and inclusion in the national curriculum, reflecting broader European and global trends that call for education systems to play a key role in preparing learners for the challenges of the 21st century. However, a lot of practical steps are necessary. Although in the Ordinance it is stated that teachers need additional training for teaching the main skills mentioned in the ordinance, practically teachers do not have concrete mechanisms for improving their teaching skills in

sustainability. In contrast, inclusion has been a key aim for almost a decade and at the current moment in most of the Bulgarian schools it is achieved through intercultural education. Intercultural education emphasizes on fostering mutual respect, tolerance, and understanding among students from diverse cultural and ethnic backgrounds. This is particularly in the Bulgarian context where ethnic minorities such as Romas and Turks live and study together. Social cohesion and minority inclusion remain ongoing priorities. Civic education, together with inclusion and green skills is another pillar of the Bulgarian curriculum which encourages active citizenship and participatory learning, aiming to equip students with the knowledge, attitudes, and skills necessary for democratic engagement. Another important policy document is the Preschool and School Education Act that institutionalizes inclusive education as a core principle and mandates differentiated support for students with special educational needs.

Despite these positive developments in recent years, there are still gaps between policy and practice. Implementation is often uneven, with disparities in resources, teacher training and institutional capacities. The disparities are especially even between schools in urban and rural areas. Furthermore, the integration of sustainability concepts tends to be thematic or extracurricular rather than deeply embedded in core curricula and subject areas. This limits the potential for systemic change and the long-term cultivation of sustainable mindsets among students.

Comparatively, a lot of EU member states are advancing comprehensive frameworks that not only include education for sustainable development (ESD) and inclusive practices but also align them with the UN's Sustainable Development Goals (particularly SDG 4). Countries such as Finland, Sweden, and Germany, for instance, integrate sustainability transversally across curricula and invest heavily in teacher training for inclusion and diversity management. Moreover, international policy instruments such as UNESCO's Education for Sustainable Development 2030 Roadmap and the European Commission's GreenComp framework provide guidance on the core competencies learners should develop to contribute to a sustainable future.

Finland

Finland's education system is internationally recognized for its commitment to equity and inclusion. Central to this commitment is the three-tiered support model, which provides general/basic, intensified, and special support to cater to diverse student needs (Finnish National Agency for Education, 2014). These levels allow educators to tailor interventions according to the needs of individual students and prevent marginalization (Kauppinen & Niemi, 2021). Finland emphasizes the importance of early intervention and flexible learning environments to ensure that all students, regardless of their background or abilities, are able to succeed. Finnish legislation, such as the Basic Education Act (628/1998), mandates the right to education and support for all students. The law stipulates that students should be educated primarily in mainstream classrooms, with necessary support measures provided

within those settings. This legal framework has contributed to the development of inclusive school cultures where collaboration among teachers, special education professionals, and guardians is encouraged. Teacher education in Finland also places a strong emphasis on inclusion, with all teachers receiving training on differentiated instruction and pedagogical strategies for diverse classrooms (Sahlberg, 2015).

However, the decentralized nature of the Finnish education system has led to variations in the implementation of inclusive practices across municipalities. This inconsistency has sometimes resulted in unintended grouping of students, potentially undermining the goals of inclusion. A significant area of concern is the integration of students with immigrant backgrounds. Despite policy frameworks promoting inclusion, these students often face challenges such as language barriers, cultural differences, and limited access to mother tongue instruction. For instance, the Finnish National Agency for Education emphasizes the importance of supporting pupils' plurilingualism and cultural identity. Yet, in practice, many immigrant students are placed in separate Finnish-as-a-second-language (S2) tracks, which can lead to feelings of isolation and hinder their academic progress (YLE News, 2024; Finnish National Agency for Education, n.d.).

Teachers play a crucial role in fostering inclusive environments. However, studies indicate that many Finnish teachers feel ill-equipped to address the needs of diverse classrooms, particularly concerning behavioral interventions and multicultural competencies (Vairimaa, 2021). Enhancing teacher training to include strategies for managing diverse classrooms and promoting cultural responsiveness is essential for the effective implementation of inclusive education. Moreover, the concentration of immigrant students in specific schools or neighborhoods has been identified as a challenge. Such clustering can limit opportunities for interaction with native Finnish speakers, thereby affecting language acquisition and integration. Teachers have expressed concerns that this segregation may impede the development of Finnish language skills among immigrant students and contribute to social isolation (Helakorpi, 2023).

While Finland's educational policies advocate for inclusion, practical challenges persist in achieving equitable outcomes for all students. Addressing these issues requires systemic efforts, including consistent implementation of inclusive practices across municipalities, enhanced teacher training, and strategies to promote integration and interaction among diverse student populations.

Greece

Greek educational policies integrate the principles of intergenerationality, identity exploration through intercultural education, and the recognition of cultural capital through

innovative communitarian strategies, such as festivals, national cuisine, and other cultural practices.

Furthermore, language learning is viewed as a key element of resilient societies, leading to the early introduction of language education in schools.

However, Greece faces significant challenges in the integration of refugees, particularly in incorporating refugee children and youth into the national curriculum. The current pedagogical approach increasingly embraces non-formal learning tools and fosters partnerships with social organizations engaged in the integration of migrant and refugee families.

In the domain of literacy, emphasis is placed on critical literacy, civic education, and raising awareness of European identity. Regarding ecology and the economy, educators seek to uncover their interconnectedness, while new forms of collective initiatives—such as social cooperatives (KOINSEP)—are beginning to emerge.

Nevertheless, the consolidation of these efforts remains difficult due to the prolonged economic crisis, and the slow assimilation of such trends within society, primarily as a result of ongoing financial hardship.

Hungary

The importance of sustainable development has been emphasized for decades at the political and member state levels. Inclusive education and sustainability are now part of pedagogical methodologies at both the international and domestic levels. Education for sustainability teaches responsible citizenship and is already appearing at the first level of public education, as a change in attitude must begin in early childhood. The transfer of knowledge requires an inclusive environment that supports the development of each student's individual abilities and skills. Inclusive education is enshrined in both legislation and strategic documents in Hungary, such as the National Public Education Act and the National Core Curriculum. Both aim to promote equal opportunities and inclusive education in classrooms. Previously, it was only applied to children with special educational needs, but now methods and programs that support diversity management and differentiated learning organization have also appeared in pedagogical practice for socially disadvantaged groups. However, achieving true inclusion in everyday education remains a challenge. Further improvements are needed in the training and awareness-raising of teachers and in the provision of the necessary resources, as school performance must be decoupled from the socio-economic status of pupils so that everyone has the opportunity to develop their abilities. Open and accessible educational spaces increase the effectiveness of education and contribute to social cohesion. One of the key elements of the long-term development of sustainable education systems in Hungary is that inclusive education and sustainability are mutually reinforcing goals in the Hungarian education system and are fully in line with

European trends and standards, promoting the education of more inclusive and sustainable future generations.

Portugal

In Portugal, inclusive education has emerged as an important dimension of the national education policy mandate, based on the principle that all the students, irrespective of their background or specific characteristics, are entitled to access, participate and achieve in the regular schools. This aspiration is underpinned by Decree-Law No. 54/2018, which reconceptualizes inclusive education as a right for all members of society and a duty of the institution, focusing on flexible curriculum development, universal design for learning, and the demotion of participation obstacles.

The Portuguese educational system encourages the inclusion of students with special educational needs, migratory backgrounds and socioeconomically disadvantaged groups in mainstream classes. This commitment is based not only on the values of equity and the dignity of the human being, but also on Portugal's adherence to international objectives as the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), more specifically Goal 4 on inclusive and equitable quality education.

In terms of policy, at the policy level, the National Strategy for Citizenship Education (ENEC) launched by the Ministry of Education has been strengthening the work with inclusion, addressing values of diversity and equality and environmental sustainability in the national curriculum. Schools are encouraged to create locally-based citizenship education plans and to implement pedagogical approaches that are inclusive and that foster empathy, participation and democratic engagement.

Portugal's policy of inclusive education is also reinforced at local level by initiatives that encourage networks of schools to pursue inclusive education. These processes include professional development for teachers, assistance for accessibility and the establishment of programs that focus on student well-being and school culture.

But even with the progress made, obstacles persist, specifically that not every school has the resources, training and institutional support necessary to do inclusivity right. Unequal-ities between urban and rural contexts are still evident, and ongoing investments in teacher training, monitoring and coordination across sectors are necessary to make sure that inclusion is not only a legal requirement, but routine practice for all students.

Romania

Romania demonstrates a growing commitment to inclusive education and sustainable development through national strategies and recent educational reforms. The National Strategy for Environmental and Climate Change Education (2023–2030) promotes a systemic and transversal integration of sustainability in education, while the National Strategy on Social Inclusion and Poverty Reduction emphasizes equity and access to quality education

for vulnerable groups, including children with disabilities, Roma communities, and those in rural areas. Inclusive education is legally supported by the National Education Law and aligned with the principles of the UN Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities.

Despite this policy framework, implementation remains uneven, particularly in under-resourced schools. The main causes are barriers such as rigid curricula, limited differentiated pedagogy, insufficient training, and lack of support for collaborative learning. There are some good Initiatives like peer mentoring, community service projects, and interdisciplinary clubs, but these often depend on individual teacher initiative rather than systemic support.

Greater autonomy in curriculum adaptation, improved teacher training on inclusive methods, and more integrated evaluation tools aligned with sustainability competencies could make a difference in inclusive education. There is a clear recognition that inclusion and sustainability are interdependent goals and that fostering both is essential for building a resilient and equitable education system.

Spain

In the case of Spain, the education system is moving toward a more inclusive model, prioritizing the integration of students with specific educational support needs into mainstream schools. This approach is not only grounded in principles of equity and normalization but also aligns with goals of social justice and sustainability. Inclusive education contributes to more cohesive, resilient, and sustainable societies, in line with the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), particularly SDG 4 (Quality Education) and SDG 10 (Reduced Inequalities).

The LOMLOE (Organic Law for the Modification of the LOE) establishes a transition toward a more inclusive system by ensuring that mainstream schools are equipped with the necessary resources to support all students, and it proposes the progressive phase-out of special education schools as a segregated model, a measure that has sparked both support and controversy among families and professionals.

In this context, the movement “Quererla es crearla” (“To Want It Is to Create It”) has gained momentum, advocating for the right of all children to learn together in inclusive settings and promoting an education system that does not exclude based on disability. This platform has played a key role in driving public and political debate on the future of inclusion in the Spanish education system.

Türkiye

Türkiye has demonstrated a growing commitment to Education for Sustainable Development (ESD) and inclusive education through its national policy frameworks, curricular reforms, and teacher training initiatives. These efforts align with the UN’s 2030 Agenda and the European

GreenComp Framework. Key national strategies—such as the 11th Development Plan, Vision 2023 Education Strategy, and the National Action Plan for Inclusive Education (2020–2023)—highlight the government’s prioritization of environmental education, equity, digital transformation, and universal access to quality education.

In the area of sustainability, Türkiye integrates environmental and eco-social topics into school curricula through project-based learning, interdisciplinary initiatives, and whole-school culture practices like recycling campaigns. According to the InclusiveFuture project’s focus group findings, participants broadly understood sustainability as encompassing environmental, social, and economic dimensions, but noted a strong overemphasis on environmental aspects at the expense of social justice and equity.

“Sustainability is about balancing today’s needs with tomorrow’s possibilities.”
“We need more focus on social justice in sustainability education.”

Teachers reported high motivation to engage students with sustainability but emphasized the need for greater access to training, time, and simplified tools to address complexity in topics like climate change, consumption, and equity. A creative example included students designing carbon-neutral school models, reflecting the integration of future thinking and student agency.

“Sustainability isn’t just one subject—it’s everything.”
“Imagining the future empowers students to act now.”

Despite the presence of sustainability values in school practice, the formal assessment of GreenComp competences remains underdeveloped. Teacher training in ESD is partially implemented, and there is a need for more systematic inclusion of GreenComp-aligned content in pedagogical approaches.

In terms of inclusive education, Türkiye has a robust legal and policy framework that ensures free access to education, promotes gender and disability inclusion, and supports disadvantaged groups through conditional cash transfers, school transportation, and textbook provision. National policy documents such as the Law on Persons with Disabilities, and compliance with the UN CRPD, provide a solid foundation.

However, focus group discussions revealed a partial and uneven implementation at the school level. Participants noted that younger students, language-minority learners, and those from disadvantaged backgrounds are often less included in sustainability-related and inclusive practices. Structural and attitudinal barriers such as rigid curricula, lack of differentiated instruction, and limited teacher capacity were also emphasized.

“Language barriers and rigid curricula limit inclusivity.”
“Inclusion starts with listening to all voices.”

Some good practices were identified, such as multilingual teaching materials, community-based learning projects, and student-led design activities that foster inclusion. Still, educators called for systemic reforms, community engagement, and stronger support mechanisms to realize the full potential of inclusive education.

General Observations from Focus Groups

- Motivation and engagement among educators are high, but time, training, and financial resources are major barriers.
- Student-led and community-oriented activities show high potential for scaling.
- There is a clear need for integrating ESD and inclusion holistically, particularly through interdisciplinary approaches and systems thinking.
- Focus group tone was hopeful and inspired, with educators expressing a strong commitment to sustainable and inclusive education despite systemic challenges.

“Small actions lead to big changes when everyone participates”

Criteria	Bulgaria	Finland	Greece	Hungary	Portugal	Romania	Spain	Türkiye
Legal framework for inclusive education	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Policies for marginalized groups	✓	◐	◐	✓	✓	✓	◐	✓
Support for students with disabilities	◐	✓	◐	✓	✓	◐	◐	◐
Provision of school meals	✓	✓	◐	✓	◐	◐	◐	◐
Free education access	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Inclusive education funding mechanisms	◐	↓	◐	◐	◐	◐	◐	◐

Table 4: Comparative Assessment of Inclusion Readiness across countries

✓ = Fully implemented

◐ = Partially implemented

✗ = Not implemented

GCI-F / TT-P = Coded descriptors for GreenComp Integration (Full) / Teacher Training (Partial)

↑ / ↓ / → = Trend indicators (where applicable)

6. Recommendations and Next Steps

6.1 General Recommendations for Policy Makers (EU or Global)

1. Integration of Sustainability Competencies Explicitly

Integrate sustainability competencies explicitly into national and regional curriculum frameworks. Define what these competencies mean, how they should be taught, and how they should be assessed. Ensure these definitions align with global frameworks like GreenComp.

2. Development of National Assessment Tools

Develop standardized national assessment tools specifically designed to evaluate sustainability competencies. These tools should be integrated into existing assessment practices and provide a clear picture of students' development in sustainability-related skills.

3. Increased Funding and Resource Allocation

Increase funding and allocate resources to support sustainability education initiatives. This includes funding for curriculum development, teacher training programs, infrastructure for eco-projects, and research on best practices in sustainability education.

4. Promotion of Interdisciplinary Collaboration

Encourage interdisciplinary collaboration at all levels of education. Facilitate the development of learning modules and projects that integrate sustainability themes across different subjects, fostering a holistic understanding of complex issues.

5. Enhancing International Cooperation

Strengthen international cooperation and knowledge exchange on sustainability education. Share best practices, research findings, and resources across countries to accelerate the development of effective sustainability education programs.

6.2 Country-Specific Recommendations and Reflections

Bulgaria: Throughout the curriculum and policy review process, several key reflections emerged. The first one is whether the integration of sustainability education is truly consistent and comprehensive across all educational levels. While there are clear guidelines for incorporating sustainability themes, such as in Ordinance № 13 and the national framework, there seem to be a gap in ensuring consistent teacher training and support for effective implementation at every school level. One constructive suggestion might be the creation of more robust professional development opportunities for teachers, particularly those in early education, to help them feel more confident in applying sustainability principles within their specific teaching contexts. Additionally, strengthening cross-sector

collaboration between environmental organizations, local communities, and schools could further enhance the practical application of sustainability education.

Despite some positive steps, there are notable gaps in the national curriculum and teacher education frameworks related to sustainability education. One such gap is the lack of a systematic, long-term approach to monitoring and evaluating sustainability education outcomes, both at the student and institutional levels. To address this, a comprehensive evaluation system should be introduced, focusing on assessing the impact of sustainability education on student behavior and the community. Another gap is the need for more practical, hands-on learning experiences, especially in rural or underserved areas, where access to sustainability projects or eco-friendly resources may be limited. Expanding outdoor education, establishing school gardens, and incorporating local environmental challenges into curriculum design could offer a more tangible and contextual learning experience.

Finland: While Finland's educational philosophy, as underlined in the national core curricula and teacher education guidelines, offer a strong foundation for Education for Sustainable Development (ESD), some critical reflections emerged for us during the review. At the national level, a key strength is the cross-curricular integration of sustainability as a value and transversal competence. However, there is a need for clearer articulation and assessment of sustainability competence(s) (?)—especially when it comes to measuring students' progress in areas like futures thinking, action competence, and systems thinking. An alignment with the GreenComp framework and its terminology could enhance consistency and shared language across the EU member states at least. A more explicit and systematic mapping of Finnish curricular goals to GreenComp domains would also support teacher training, resource development, and cross-country collaboration.

From this very initial policy and research analysis, it seems like a noticeable gap lies in teacher education and professional development, where sustainability is often present in theory but not sufficiently operationalised in practice. Teacher educators need concrete tools, pedagogical models, and assessment strategies that help embed sustainability competences meaningfully in teaching. National policies also lack monitoring mechanisms to ensure that ESD is consistently implemented across schools and regions. To address this, there is a need to introduce sustainability training for (in-service) teachers, strengthen peer learning networks, and support schools in developing whole-school sustainability strategies. Based on our understanding from the document reviews, implementing ESD is most impactful when it is embedded in the school culture—for example, through student-led projects, collaboration with local communities, and open dialogues on global justice. “Municipalities should encourage collaborative efforts to address sustainability challenges at a grassroots level, ensuring that changes in knowledge and attitudes extend beyond schools and into the wider community. Schools can plan and execute sustainability renewal programs and renovations more easily if they are planned together.”

Greece: European curricula often heavily emphasize examinations. This focus is compounded by several factors: school architecture and building design, the urban location of many schools, a lack of green spaces, the organization of excursions, learning confined to the classroom, and a disconnect from the relief offered by a child's direct experience with the local landscape. Furthermore, there is a tendency towards excessive theorization of knowledge and a detached approach to subjects like mathematics, geometry, economics, and geography, separated from the study of natural and social environments. Hence the curricula as well as the schools need to go beyond subject boundaries and take a more holistic approach to learning and development of young pupils.

Hungary: There were several key gaps identified, particularly the lack of practical training and professional development opportunities for educators and school leaders that is relevant to sustainability education. Sustainability is conceptualized in several ways—it is not always operationalized in teacher training, leaving prospective teachers few concrete tools, strategies, and methods for assessment that support the effective integration of sustainability into their daily practices. Another important gap is the lack of standardised national assessment frameworks designed around sustainability competences that can result in disjointed and inconsistent implementation.

Portugal: Inclusion is certainly an important vector in education that needs to be looked at from different perspectives. While at the same time one must promote the knowledge in function of different realities, especially when it comes to guarantee free public education, but also access to school for all and differentiated learning. In a time when everybody is stressed about counting results and promoting school success measured by numbers, essentially related to certain subjects, the discussion of inclusion in public schools is pertinent and imperative. Education and teacher training shall not be used to implement processes and practices that jeopardise the equality and diversity of every human being. In fact, inclusion, in its many aspects, does not mean that one has to implement an overall standard to everyone. A more thoughtful inclusive practice shall take into account the diversity based on the intrinsic realities of children and young students. So, a certain reflection on standardisation of curricular practices is necessary.

Romania: In environmental education, in addition to the acquisition of knowledge, emotional influence and habit formation are equally important in early childhood. In order for the students to consider it really important, to acquire the values they have learned, they need to spend time in nature: walking, hiking, field trips, forest school, visits, etc.

"One day in the mountains is equal to a mountain of books". Time (modules in the framework curriculum) and financial resources must be spent on this – in teacher training, formal and non-formal education alike. Among the school-leaving exams there are foreign language and digital competencies, but competencies regarding sustainability are missing. It would be necessary to indicate the importance of these competencies to the students, parents and society.

In primary schools, despite the fact that the range of elective subjects includes offers related to sustainability education, due to the large number of lessons per week, parents and students often opt for the minimum number of optional lessons and prefer those that help students prepare for admission and learn a foreign language. The concept of sustainability is introduced and used but takes on a completely different meaning when its four dimensions are analyzed and discussed in different lessons.

In teacher training, teachers should become familiar with the opportunities for environmental education outside the classroom, be able to professionally plan visits and excursions – both from an organizational and content point of view – and be motivated to take advantage of opportunities outside the classroom.

Spain: We believe that the curriculum should clearly identify the points on sustainability competences to be improved, helping the students to better understand them and how to start thinking about improvements. Sometimes the curriculum itself is not sustainable enough. It should provide more tools or ideas in its programme to widen the options for students and schools to start discussing and facing sustainability issues.

Türkiye: One critical gap in the Turkish national curriculum is the absence of a unified sustainability education framework. Although relevant values and goals are embedded across subjects, there is a need to systematize sustainability competencies into a coherent cross-curricular policy. Moreover, teacher and school leader training programs require stronger integration of GreenComp-associated with practices to build instructional capacity.

It is recommended that national policies adopt a whole-school approach to sustainability, including operational models, assessment frameworks, and community partnerships. Policy-makers should also prioritize interdisciplinary materials and training to enable teachers to embed sustainability values across disciplines. The pedagogical model developed under the InclusiveFuture project could serve as a pilot framework for national implementation in Türkiye.

6.3 Teacher Education Programs (For Pre-Service Teachers)

1. Comprehensive Sustainability Training

Incorporate comprehensive sustainability training into all pre-service teacher education programs. This training should include theoretical knowledge, practical skills, and pedagogical approaches for teaching sustainability.

2. Focus on Action Competence

Emphasize the development of action competence in teachers. Equip pre-service teachers with strategies to translate knowledge into action, both in their own lives and in their classrooms, encouraging student agency and participation in sustainability initiatives.

3. Integration of GreenComp Framework

Integrate the GreenComp framework into teacher education curricula. Ensure pre-service teachers understand the different dimensions of sustainability and are prepared to teach and assess these competencies.

4. Experiential Learning

Include experiential learning opportunities in teacher education programs. Provide pre-service teachers with practical experience in leading eco-projects, outdoor activities, and community engagement initiatives.

5. Assessment Literacy

Develop teachers' assessment literacy in relation to sustainability competencies. Train pre-service teachers to use formative, holistic, and competence-based assessment methods that accurately evaluate students' sustainability skills and knowledge.

6.4 Teacher Professional Development Programs (For In-Service Teachers)

1. Ongoing Training Opportunities

Provide ongoing professional development opportunities for in-service teachers focused on sustainability education. Offer workshops, seminars, and online courses that cover new pedagogical approaches, assessment tools, and curriculum resources.

2. Collaboration and Networking

Facilitate collaboration and networking among teachers interested in sustainability education. Create platforms for teachers to share best practices, discuss challenges, and develop collaborative projects.

3. Support for Interdisciplinary Teaching

Provide specific support and training for interdisciplinary teaching. Offer guidance on integrating sustainability themes across different subjects and developing interdisciplinary learning modules.

4. Mentoring and Coaching

Implement mentoring and coaching programs where experienced teachers can support their colleagues in integrating sustainability into their teaching practice.

5. Integration of Local Contexts

Tailor professional development programs to local contexts and challenges. Provide teachers with resources and strategies for addressing specific environmental and social issues in their communities.

6.5 Support for School Leaders

1. Leadership Training

Provide leadership training on sustainable school management. Equip school leaders with the knowledge and skills to implement whole-school approaches to sustainability, promote teacher collaboration, and manage eco-projects.

2. Creating a Sustainable School Culture

Encourage school leaders to create a sustainable school culture. This includes integrating sustainability into school policies, routines, and infrastructure, as well as fostering a sense of community and shared responsibility for the environment.

3. Supporting Teacher Autonomy

School leaders must be able to create space for and support teacher autonomy in developing and implementing sustainability education initiatives as well as provide resources, guidance, and flexibility for teachers to innovate and adapt their teaching practices to address sustainability issues.

4. Stakeholder Engagement

Promote stakeholder engagement, including students, parents, and the wider community, in sustainability initiatives. Encourage school leaders to establish partnerships with local organizations and involve students in decision-making processes.

5. Data Collection and Reporting

Support school leaders in collecting and reporting data on sustainability initiatives and outcomes. This data can be used to monitor progress, identify areas for improvement, and share successes with the wider community.

6.6 Next Steps for the Project

1. Collect supplementary data from schools and educators

Project partners will conduct focus group discussions with teachers and educators at the respective schools in their partner countries to gather supplementary data from the field. This data will then be combined with learnings and recommendations from this report in order to create a complete picture of the latest progress and readiness levels of the countries in terms of Education for Sustainable Development.

2. Compilation of best practices

Based on the results of this study as well as the focus group report, good practices from each country will be explored and compiled for generating inspiration through examples

3. Preparation of an Inclusive pedagogical model on embedding sustainability competences in education

Once the understanding of good practices, needs and gaps is built, an inclusive pedagogical model will be prepared to provide guidance to teachers and educators on integrating inclusivity and sustainability principles and practices in schools

4. Develop and pilot an online course for teachers to provide guidance on the application of the developed model

The created pedagogical model shall be piloted through an online course that will provide detailed guidance to teachers on using the model through demonstration of exemplary practices. The course will serve as a pilot programme based on the recommendations provided in this document as well as focus group reports.

5. Monitoring and evaluation

An ongoing and comprehensive monitoring and evaluation framework will be implemented throughout the pilot course. This continuous assessment will involve the systematic collection and analysis of data related to various aspects of the course. Feedback will be gathered from relevant stakeholders through surveys and interviews. The data collected will be used to identify areas for improvement and inform necessary adjustments to the course content, delivery methods, and assessment strategies. This iterative approach to course development will ensure that the pilot course remains dynamic, responsive to the needs of learners, and aligned with the intended learning objectives, ultimately leading to a more robust and effective learning experience.

6.7 Risk Factors and Mitigation Suggestions

Even though the recommendations and suggested actions are well-supported by varied data sources, implementing new measures or altering policies and practices invariably carries risks. Table 5 outlines potential risks alongside corresponding mitigation strategies for each risk factor.

Risk	Mitigation
Lack of Political Will or Support	Engage with policymakers early and often. Present evidence of the benefits of sustainability education. Build alliances with NGOs and community groups.
Teacher Resistance or Lack of Capacity	Provide ongoing professional development and support. Address concerns with practical strategies and resources. Highlight success stories and showcase effective integration.

<p>Insufficient Funding or Resources</p>	<p>Develop a realistic budget and seek diverse funding. Leverage existing resources and partnerships. Demonstrate the cost-effectiveness of initiatives.</p>
<p>Difficulty in Assessing Sustainability Competencies</p>	<p>Develop clear assessment tools and guidelines. Provide teacher training on assessment methods. Use varied approaches: formative, summative, and portfolio.</p>
<p>Implementation Challenges in Diverse Contexts</p>	<p>Adapt recommendations to local contexts and needs. Provide flexibility and support for tailoring initiatives. Foster collaboration and knowledge sharing among schools.</p>
<p>Lack of Student Engagement</p>	<p>Develop engaging and relevant learning activities. Involve students in decision-making and leadership. Connect sustainability to real-world issues and local contexts.</p>

Table 5: Probable risk factors and corresponding mitigation measures possible during the implementation of recommended policy and practice suggestions

By implementing these recommendations, minimizing and proactively addressing potential risks, countries can contribute to the development of effective and impactful sustainability education programs that empower learners to create a more sustainable future.

7. Conclusion

This comprehensive curricular mapping study reveals a consistent global trend toward integrating sustainability principles into national education systems. Across all eight examined countries—Bulgaria, Finland, Greece, Hungary, Portugal, Romania, Spain, and Türkiye—there is a shared recognition of the importance of environmental, social, and cultural sustainability. Curricula increasingly emphasize interdisciplinary approaches, systems thinking, and project-based learning to equip students with the knowledge, skills, and values necessary for addressing complex sustainability challenges. Notably, while environmental sustainability often takes precedence, social sustainability is also gaining prominence, reflecting a broader understanding of interconnected global issues and the need for equitable, inclusive societies.

However, despite these commonalities, significant differences and country-specific challenges persist. Teacher training, the assessment of sustainability competencies, and the practical implementation of interdisciplinary approaches emerge as recurring areas needing improvement. Many countries report that while teachers acknowledge the importance of sustainability, they often lack the confidence or concrete tools to effectively integrate it into their teaching practices. Additionally, standardized assessment frameworks for sustainability competencies are frequently absent, hindering the ability to track progress and ensure accountability. Balancing formal education requirements with experiential, hands-on learning also remains a widespread challenge, as exam-focused systems and time constraints can impede the practical application of sustainability principles.

In conclusion, while all analyzed countries demonstrate a commitment to sustainability education, the degree of explicit integration, the effectiveness of implementation, and the level of alignment with frameworks like GreenComp vary considerably. Addressing the identified gaps through enhanced teacher training, robust assessment methodologies, and increased opportunities for experiential learning is crucial for advancing sustainability education globally. Collaboration and knowledge sharing among countries, along with continuous evaluation and adaptation of curricula, will be essential in fostering a generation of responsible and capable global citizens equipped to build a more sustainable and just future.

8. Bibliography

1. Bianchi, G., Pisiotis, U., & Cabrera Giraldez, M. (2022). *GreenComp: The European sustainability competence framework*. Publications Office of the European Union. <https://doi.org/10.2760/13286>
2. Camões, A. T., Figueiredo, I. L., Cardoso, J., & all. (2016). *Development Education Guidelines – Preschool Education, Basic Education and Secondary Education*. https://cidadania.dge.mec.pt/sites/default/files/pdfs/developmenteducationguidelinespreschool_educationbasiceducationandsecondaryeducation.pdf
3. Câmara, A. C., Proença, A., & Teixeira, F. (2018). *Environmental Education for Sustainability* (in PT). Directorate-General for Education. https://www.dge.mec.pt/sites/default/files/ECidadania/Educacao_Ambiental/documentos/referencial_ambiente.pdf
4. Directorate-General for Education. (2012). *National Curriculum for Basic Education - Core Competencies* (in PT). https://metasdeaprendizagem.dge.mec.pt/metasdeaprendizagem.dge.mec.pt/wp-content/uploads/2010/09/Curriculo_Nacional1CEB.pdf
5. Directorate-General for Education. (2017). *National Strategy for Citizenship Education*. https://www.dge.mec.pt/sites/default/files/Projetos_Curriculares/Aprendizagens_Essenciais/estrategia_cidadania.pdf?utm_source=chatgpt.com
6. Directorate-General for Education & Camões Institute. (2018). *Strategy for Development Education 2018–2022* (in PT). <https://cidadania.dge.mec.pt/sites/default/files/pdfs/ened2018-2022portugues.pdf>
7. European Commission. (2018). *Council Recommendation of 22 May 2018 on key competences for lifelong learning*. [https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32018H0604\(01\)&from=EN](https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32018H0604(01)&from=EN)
8. European Commission. (2020). *A European Green Deal*. https://ec.europa.eu/info/strategy/priorities-2019-2024/european-green-deal_en#documents
9. European Commission. (2020). *Circular Economy Action Plan: For a cleaner and more competitive Europe*. https://ec.europa.eu/environment/topics/circular-economy/first-circular-economy-action-plan_en
10. European Commission. (2020). *European Skills Agenda for sustainable competitiveness, social fairness and resilience*. <https://ec.europa.eu/social/main.jsp?catid=1223&langId=en>
11. European Commission. (2020). *Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions on*

achieving the European Education Area by 2025.
https://ec.europa.eu/education/education-in-the-eu/european-education-area_en

12. European Commission. (2022). *GreenComp: The European sustainability competence framework* (Publication No. JRC128040). Publications Office of the European Union. <https://publications.jrc.ec.europa.eu/repository/handle/JRC128040>
13. European Commission. Directorate General for Education, Youth, Sport and Culture. (2024). *Monitoring learning for sustainability: Developing a cross EU approach: Final report*. Publications Office. <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2766/653214>
14. EU Biodiversity Strategy: *Bringing Nature Back into Our Lives*. (2020). https://ec.europa.eu/environment/strategy/biodiversity-strategy-2030_en
15. Finnish National Agency for Education. (2014). *National core curriculum for basic education 2014*. <https://www.oph.fi/en/statistics-and-publications/publications/national-core-curriculum-basic-education-2014>
16. Finnish National Agency for Education. (2019). *National core curriculum for general upper secondary schools 2019* (English translation, 2024 update). <https://www.oph.fi/en/statistics-and-publications/publications/national-core-curriculum-general-upper-secondary-schools-2019>
17. Finnish National Agency for Education. (n.d.). *Education and support for pupils with migrant and multilingual background*. Retrieved from <https://www.oph.fi/en/education-and-qualifications/education-and-support-pupils-migrant-and-multilingual-background>
18. Government Gazette. (2021). *Government Gazette 3567 B 04-08-2021, Government Gazette 3791 B 13-08-2021*.
19. Government of Spain. (2021). *Estrategia de Educación para el Desarrollo Sostenible 2030 [Education for Sustainable Development Strategy 2030]*. Ministerio para la Transición Ecológica y el Reto Demográfico. <https://www.miteco.gob.es/es/cambio-climatico/temas/educacion-ambiental/estrategia-de-educacion-para-el-desarrollo-sostenible-2030.aspx>
20. Government of Spain. (2022). *Real Decreto 157/2022, de 1 de marzo, por el que se establecen la ordenación y las enseñanzas mínimas de la Educación Primaria* [Royal Decree 157/2022, of March 1, establishing the organization and minimum teachings of Primary Education]. *Boletín Oficial del Estado* (núm. 52), 24853–24972. <https://www.boe.es/eli/es/rd/2022/03/01/157>
21. Government of Spain. (2022). *Real Decreto 217/2022, de 29 de marzo, por el que se establece la ordenación y las enseñanzas mínimas de la Educación Secundaria Obligatoria* [Royal Decree 217/2022, of March 29, which establishes the organization and minimum teaching of Compulsory Secondary Education]. *Boletín Oficial del Estado* (núm. 76), 41980–42078. <https://www.boe.es/eli/es/rd/2022/03/29/217>
22. Helakorpi, J., Holm, G., & Liu, X. (2023). Education of pupils with migrant backgrounds: A systemic failure in the Finnish system? In M. Thrupp, P. Seppänen, J. Kauko, & S. Kosunen (Eds.), *Finland's famous education system* (pp. 319–333). Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-19-8241-5_20

23. Institute of Educational Policy. (n.d.). *Πρωτοβάθμια εκπαίδευση: Μονάδα προσχολικής αγωγής και εκπαίδευσης* [Primary education: Preschool education unit]. Retrieved May 29, 2025, from <https://www.iep.edu.gr/el/primary-education-yliko/mon-prosx-yliko-2023-2024>
24. IEP.edu.gr. (n.d.-a). *Curriculum for Gymnasium*. <https://ebooks.edu.gr/ebooks/v2/ps.jsp>
25. IEP.edu.gr. (n.d.-b). *National Core Curriculum for School Education (grades 1–12)*.
26. IEP.edu.gr. (n.d.-c). *New educational programs: Primary school and Secondary school*. <https://iep.edu.gr/el/nea-programmata-spoudon-arxiki-selida>
27. Joint Research Centre. (2022). *GreenComp: The European sustainability competence framework*. European Commission. <https://doi.org/10.2760/094757>
28. Kauppinen, H., & Niemi, P. (2021). The 21st Century Reforms (Re)Shaping the Education Policy of Inclusive and Special Education in Finland. *Education Sciences*, 11 (11), 750. <https://doi.org/10.3390/educsci11110750>
29. Kortetmäki, T., Heikkinen, H. L. T., & Lehtonen, A. (2021). Planetary well-being. *Environmental Values*, 30(3), 289–306. <https://doi.org/10.3197/096327121X16141625587538>
30. Lagartixa, C., & Alves, M. (2024). *On the trail of Continuing Teacher Education (in PT)*. Custódio Lagartixa & Marta Alves (Eds.). Montijo. <https://afc.dge.mec.pt/sites/default/files/2024-02/Nos%20Trilhos%20da%20Forma%C3%A7%C3%A3o%20Cont%C3%ADnua%20de%20Professores%20-%20%20Reflex%C3%B5es%2C%20olhares%20e%20testemunhos.pdf>
31. Lambrechts, W., Van Liedekerke, L., & Van Petegem, P. (2018). The impact of organisational culture on the integration of sustainable development into higher education institutions. *International Journal of Sustainability in Higher Education*, 19(6), 975–991.
32. Lozano, R. (2011). The state of sustainable development in higher education institutions: Comparing the reports they produce. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 19(1), 76–83.
33. Law on Pre-school and School Education in Bulgaria. (n.d.). <https://www.navet.government.bg/bg/media/ZAKON-ZA-PREDUCHILISHTNOTO-I-UCHILISHNOTO-OBRAZOVANIE.pdf>
34. Merza, A., Kardon, B., & Kormos, F. (2024). *Researchers' Night in Europe 2024 – Interview on one of the most exciting science show events of the year and the Hungarian example*. RCISD. https://rcisd.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/11/Synergies_publ_24.pdf
35. Ministerio de Educación y Ciencia. (2007). *Real Decreto 276/2007, de 23 de febrero, por el que se aprueba el reglamento de ingreso, accesos y adquisición de nuevas especialidades en los cuerpos docentes* [Royal Decree 276/2007, of February 23, which approves the regulations for entry, access and acquisition of new specialties in the teaching bodies]. *Boletín Oficial del Estado* (53), 9374–9416. <https://www.boe.es/eli/es/rd/2007/02/23/276>
36. Ministerio de la Presidencia, Relaciones con las Cortes y Memoria Democrática. (2020). *Ley Orgánica 3/2020, de 29 de diciembre, por la que se modifica la Ley Orgánica 2/2006, de 3 de mayo, de Educación (LOMLOE)* [Organic Law 3/2020, of December 29, which modifies Organic Law 2/2006, of May 3, on Education]. *Boletín Oficial del Estado* (340), 122868–123000. <https://www.boe.es/eli/es/lo/2020/12/29/3/con>

37. Ministerul Educației, România. (2022). *Strategia Națională privind Educația pentru mediu și schimbări climatice* [National Strategy on Education for the Environment and Climate Change]. https://www.edu.ro/sites/default/files/_fi%C8%99iere/Strategii/SNEMSC_2023_2030.pdf
38. Mogensen, F., & Schnack, K. (2010). The action competence approach and the 'new' discourses of education for sustainable development. *Environmental Education Research*, 16(1), 59–74. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13504620903504032>
39. Nagy Eszter & dr. Nagy Lászlóné. (2014). *A fenntarthatóság pedagógiájának elemei és megjelenésük a központi tantervekben a bevezető, kezdő és alapozó iskolaszakaszokban* [The pedagogy of sustainability and its elements in the central curricula in the introductory, beginner and basic school sections]. Mozaik Kiadó.
40. Oinonen, I., Seppälä, T., & Paloniemi, R. (2024). How does action competence explain young people's sustainability action? *Environmental Education Research*, 30(4), 499–518. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13504622.2023.2241675>
41. Ordinance No. 13 of 21 September 2016 on Civic, Health, Environmental, and Intercultural Education. Retrieved from https://ruo-sofia-grad.com/wp-content/uploads/2025/04/22_0.pdf
42. Sala, A., Punie, Y., Garkov, V., & Cabrera Giraldez, M. (2020). *LifeComp: The European Framework for Personal, Social and Learning to Learn Key Competence*. Joint Research Centre, European Commission. <https://ec.europa.eu/jrc/en/lifecom>
43. UNESCO. (2009). *Education for Sustainable Development Lens: Learning and Training Tools*. UNESCO.
44. UNESCO. (2017). *Education for Sustainable Development Goals: Learning objectives*. <https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000247444>
45. UNESCO. (2020). *Education for sustainable development: A roadmap*. <https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000374802>
46. Vairimaa, R. (2020). *How should we implement inclusive education?* University of Helsinki. Retrieved from <https://www.helsinki.fi/en/news/finnish-schools/how-should-we-implement-inclusive-education>
47. Yle News. (2024, October 31). "The Finnish education system isn't designed for immigrant children" — Foreign parents fear S2 track holds kids back. Retrieved from: <https://yle.fi/a/74-20121477>